

Implementation of the Citizen's Charter Provision of Republic Act 11032 and Service Delivery Satisfaction Among the Barangays of Naic, Cavite

Justin Jeffrey C. Boquiron, LPT, MPS
Cavite State University
justinjeffrey.boquiron@cvsu.edu.ph

Maria Soledad M. Lising, PhD
Cavite State University
mariel_lising@cvsu.edu.ph

Date Submitted:
January 12, 2026

Date Accepted:
February 7, 2026

Date Published:
February 21, 2026

DOI:
10.5281/zenodo.18726208

ABSTRACT

This study assessed the level of implementation of the Citizen's Charter provision of Republic Act No. 11032 in the barangays of the Municipality of Naic and examined its impact on client satisfaction in service delivery using a descriptive-correlational research design. Data were gathered from 450 clients who availed of various barangay services through a printed survey questionnaire covering respondents' demographic profile, level of Citizen's Charter implementation, and satisfaction with service delivery. Statistical tools such as frequency and percentage distribution, median, Kruskal-Wallis test, one-way ANOVA, Mann-Whitney U test, Friedman two-way ANOVA, and Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test were

employed for data analysis. Results showed that most respondents were aged 25 to 34, while the fewest were 55 years old and above. Male and female respondents were almost equally represented, nearly half were married, and the majority were college-educated, employed, and earning a monthly income of ₱21,194 and below. Barangay clearances and certificates were the most frequently availed services, followed by business clearances, while facility use and blotter services were the least utilized. Findings further revealed a significant correlation between the level of Citizen's Charter implementation and client satisfaction, indicating that improved implementation leads to higher satisfaction in service delivery. The study underscores the importance of strengthening compliance with established service standards, regularly reviewing procedures, and enhancing feedback mechanisms to improve service efficiency, transparency, and accountability in barangay governance while ensuring adherence to existing laws, guidelines, and regulations.

Keywords: *Citizen's Charter, Republic Act No. 11032, Barangay Service Delivery, Client Satisfaction, Public Service Implementation, Local Governance, Descriptive-Correlational Study*

INTRODUCTION

The Republic Act No. 11032, otherwise known as the “Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018,” was signed into law by then-President Rodrigo Duterte in 2018. This law amends the RA 9485 or Anti-Red Tape Act of 2007, aiming to address the persistent issues of bureaucratic red tapes that contribute to graft and corruption. By reengineering systems, simplifying requirements, and procedures, the law seeks to improve turnaround times and promote transparency and accountability in both business and non-business transactions within public service.

Transparency plays a crucial role in increasing accountability, as it helps to eliminate inefficient and corrupt practices within the government (Gabriel, 2018). The public, as clients of government services, have the right to demand quality and prompt service. Citizen engagement is essential in applying pressure on service providers and controlling corruption, which is considered a critical aspect of government reform (Brillantes & Fernandez, 2011).

The culture of graft and corruption is one of the factors that contributes to a spoil system in Philippine bureaucracy that restricts the efficiency of government services and assassinate the neutrality in politics (Caren, 2012). In 2010 Annual Poverty Indicators Survey (APIS) conducted by the Philippine National Statistics Office in 2010 revealed that 75 percent of families with at least one member is supply driven or voluntarily gave money, gift or favor in exchange of ease in transaction, while the other 25 percent were demand-driven. Less than 1 percent of those who did not voluntarily give pecuniary reported the incident, (as cited by Hays 2018).

To address bureaucratic red tape, RA 9485 or the Anti-Red Tape Act of 2007 was enacted and later amended by RA 11032, the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018. The amendment streamlines public services by simplifying processes, reducing requirements, and ensuring timely responses to client transactions. A key feature is the Citizen’s Charter, which outlines agency services and promotes a citizen-centered approach to minimize delays, excessive requirements, and transaction costs.

According to Calina (2015), the Citizen’s Charter treats citizens as citizen-consumers since it is propagated under the New Public Administration Model. The idea is to replace consumer rights with political and legal rights. The citizens are considered consumers of government services; hence should be the ultimate judge on the quality of services provided by the public institutions.

Despite the passage of these laws, significant improvements remain limited. The 2022 ARTA Report Card Survey 2.0 showed that 37.5 percent of agencies need to review RA 11032, with only 25 percent rated satisfactory, 12.5 percent very satisfactory, 12.5 percent compliant, and 12.5% needing improvement. Similarly, a 2018 Ombudsman report revealed that LGUs received the most corruption-related complaints for seven straight years, with 1,065 of 3,189 cases in 2017 involving barangays.

In the 2023 Cities and Municipalities Competitiveness Index (CMCI), Naic, Cavite achieved a score of 8.9880 in the Government Efficiency pillar. This pillar evaluates various aspects of local

government performance, including the quality of public services, compliance with national policies, and the promotion of a business-friendly environment. A score of 8.9880 suggests that Naic's local government units demonstrate a high level of efficiency in these areas.

Notably, Naic ranked 1st in compliance with the Anti-Red Tape Act (ARTA) Citizen's Charter, reflecting a strong commitment to reducing bureaucratic red tape and enhancing transparency and accountability in public service delivery. This high ranking indicates that the municipality has made significant strides in implementing governance reforms and providing efficient services to its constituents.

Given these achievements, it is relevant to examine how well the Citizen's Charter provisions are being implemented in practice. This study will therefore explore the level of implementation of the Citizen's Charter at the barangay level, where most citizen transactions occur. The goal is to assess its impact on improving government efficiency and service delivery in the locality.

The services of the barangay, as outlined in the Citizen's Charter include the issuance of certificates for individuals and businesses, as well as the maintenance of a blotter for recording incidents. Barangays issue various certifications, such as barangay clearances and certificates of residency, which are required for purposes like employment, business permits, or other legal matters. These certificates serve as official documents confirming an individual's identity or residency within the barangay and are essential for residents to access government services or comply with local regulations. Additionally, barangays maintain a blotter, which records incidents or complaints reported by residents, including disturbances, minor offenses, and disputes. These frontline services are vital for ensuring smooth governance at the barangay level, facilitating residents' interaction with local government, and contributing to the overall safety and order of the community.

Statement of the Problem

The study generally intended to assess the implementation of the Citizen's Charter provision of RA 11032 and service delivery satisfaction among the barangays in the Naic, Cavite.

The study specifically aimed to assess the following:

1. What is the client's demographic profile in terms of the following:
 - a. age;
 - b. sex;
 - c. civil status;
 - d. highest educational attainment;
 - e. employment status;
 - f. monthly income, and

- a. age;
 - b. sex;
 - c. civil status;
 - d. highest educational attainment;
 - e. employment status;
 - f. monthly income, and
 - g. service availed;
2. Identify the level of implementation of the Citizens Charter provision of RA 11032 in terms of the following:
- a. uniform/standard requirements;
 - b. procedure to obtain a particular service;
 - c. person/s responsible for each step;
 - d. maximum time to conclude the process;
 - e. document/s to be presented by the client, if necessary;
 - f. amount of fees, if necessary, and
 - g. procedure for filing complaints;
3. Determine the level of client satisfaction in the service delivery in terms of:
- a. customer service; and
 - b. quality of service;
4. Identify if there is a significant difference in the following indicators when the clients are grouped according to the demographic profile:
- a. implementation of the Citizen's Charter; and
 - b. client satisfaction;
5. Identify if there is a significant difference among the indicators in the following:
- a. implementation of the Citizen's Charter; and
 - b. client satisfaction; and

-
6. Identify if there is a significant relationship between the level of implementation and level of client satisfaction.

Hypotheses of the Study

The following hypotheses of the study were tested using statistical analysis to realize the objective and answer the statement of the problem.

Ho1 There is no significant difference in the following indicators when the participants are grouped according to the client's demographics in the following:

- a. implementation of the Citizen's Charter
- b. client Satisfaction

Ho2 There is no significant difference among indicators in the level of implementation and level of client satisfaction.

Ho3 There is no significant relationship between the level of implementation and level of client satisfaction.

Significance of the Study

The result of the study would be deemed significant to the following:

Local Government of the Municipality of Naic. This may offer critical insights into service delivery gaps and areas for enhancement, facilitating the refinement of processes and boosting public satisfaction.

Barangay Councils. This may help identify the performance level of barangay officials and employees in delivering services as provided in the citizens charter.

Department of Interior and Local Government. This may provide additional information to support the DILG's role in monitoring local government compliance with national policies, helping to target interventions, capacity-building programs, and support.

Anti-Red Tape Authority. This may assist ARTA in tracking the compliance of local government units with RA 11032, helping to identify which areas require enforcement or support.

Citizens. This may impact the quality-of-service citizens receive, as the findings can lead to improvements in service delivery mechanisms with the empower citizens about their rights to efficient and timely government services, promoting civic engagement and participation.

Future researchers. This may provide a valuable reference point for future research on public administration, governance, and policy implementation, particularly in local government setting.

Time and Place of the Study

This study was conducted from January to February 2025 in the Municipality of Naic, Province of Cavite, with a specific focus on all its barangays. Naic was chosen as the study area due to its outstanding performance in the 2023 Cities and Municipalities Competitiveness Index (CMCI), where the municipal government ranked first in compliance with the Anti-Red Tape Authority (ARTA) Citizen's Charter under the Government Efficiency pillar. Given this recognition at the municipal level, it is equally important to examine how the standards of the Citizen's Charter are implemented at the barangay level and how these standards influence service delivery. Doing so provides a more comprehensive understanding of service delivery across all levels of local governance and helps assess whether the effectiveness observed at the municipal level is reflected at the grassroots level.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This was conducted to determine the level of implementation of the Citizen's Charter provision of RA 11032 and limited only to the Uniform/Standard requirements; procedure to obtain a particular service; person/s responsible for each step; the maximum time to conclude the process; document's to be presented by the customer, if necessary; amount of fees, if necessary; and the procedure for filing complaints. It also discloses the client satisfaction with the service delivery in terms of customer service and quality of service. The clients of the study will be the Barangay's clients with direct business and non-business-related transactions.

Definition of Terms

Barangay refers to the smallest administrative unit in the Philippines, tasked with delivering public services.

Business-related transaction refers to any interaction, process, or exchange involving a business entity. This includes the filing, approval, renewal, or obtaining of permits, licenses, certificates, clearances, and other similar documents as stated in the Citizen's Charter relative to business. The transaction is governed by regulatory requirements and should adhere to the prescribed maximum processing time.

Citizens' charter refers to an official document, a service standard, or a pledge that communicates, in simple terms, information on the services provided by the government to its citizens pursuant to Section 6 of Republic Act 11032. It describes in detail the comprehensive and uniform checklist of requirements for each type of application or request; procedure to obtain a particular service; person/s responsible for each step; maximum time to conclude the process; document/s to be presented by the applicant or requesting party; if necessary; amount of fees, if necessary; and procedure for filing complaints.

Client or participant refers to individuals and beneficiaries of the services provided within the jurisdiction of the barangay in the Municipality of Naic. These individuals interact with and utilize barangay services.

Client satisfaction refers to the degree to which clients' expectations and needs are met by the service delivery as outlined in the Citizen's Charter.

Customer service refers to the quality of interactions between staff and clients, characterized by friendly and courteous assistance, timely response to inquiries, professionalism in addressing concerns, and competence in handling requests. It also includes clear communication, a genuine willingness to help, and the ability to resolve issues within a reasonable time frame.

Ease of doing business refers to the simplicity, efficiency, and overall friendliness of a country's regulatory environment in relation to starting and operating a business.

Frontline services refers to the services outlined in the barangay's Citizen's Charter, primarily including the issuance of various clearances and certificates that are essential for constituents and local businesses. This encompasses constituents' clearances, business establishment or owner clearances, and the maintenance of a blotter that records community incidents.

Implementation refers to the practical application and execution of the requirements and standards outlined in the Citizen's Charter by government agencies and local government units, including the barangays.

Local Government Unit refers to political subdivisions established by or in accordance with the Constitution, composed of provinces, cities, municipalities, barangays, and autonomous regions.

Non-business-related transaction refers to any interaction or process with an individual or group of individuals that does not pertain to business operations or business regulation. The services include personal documents of the individual, not directly related to business activities. The transaction governs regulatory requirements and should adhere to the prescribed maximum processing time.

Non-working refers to a person who is not engaged in any form of economic activity and is not looking for a job.

Quality of service refers to how well the barangay meets client expectations in delivering public services. It includes responsiveness, reliability, professionalism, accountability, and accessibility.

Red tape refers to excessive bureaucracy or adherence to formal rules and procedures that are considered redundant, overly complex, or time-consuming, especially in the context of governmental and administrative processes.

Unemployed refers to a person who is not currently working, is actively seeking employment, and is available to work.

Theoretical Framework of the Study

This study is anchored in the New Public Management (NPM) theory, popularized by Christopher Hood in his seminal 1991 article "A Public Management for All Seasons?". NPM has significantly

influenced modern public sector reforms, particularly in transforming how government institutions deliver services and interact with citizens. At its core, NPM advocates for the adoption of private sector principles—such as efficiency, accountability, performance measurement, and customer orientation—within public sector operations. Pollitt and Bouckaert (2011) emphasize that these principles have been widely implemented in various administrative systems to enhance service delivery and public sector performance.

The relevance of NPM to this study lies in its utility in assessing the implementation and outcomes of the Citizens' Charter at the local level. The Citizens' Charter, mandated by the Anti-Red Tape Act of 2007 (RA 9485) and strengthened by RA 11032 or the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018, embodies core NPM ideals by setting clear service standards, streamlining procedures, and promoting transparency and accountability in government transactions.

One of NPM's key contributions is its emphasis on efficiency as a guiding principle in public administration. Pollitt and Bouckaert (2011) highlight that NPM reforms aim to make public services more streamlined, performance-driven, and results-oriented, drawing on private sector management techniques. In the context of this study, the Citizens' Charter serves as a concrete tool for operationalizing efficiency by reducing bureaucratic delays, clarifying service processes, and ensuring timely delivery, all of which directly influence client satisfaction. More recently, Lapuente and Van de Walle (2020) argue that while NPM-driven strategies have improved efficiency in some cases, their success is highly dependent on implementation capacity and institutional context. Thus, this study will utilize NPM's efficiency lens to examine whether the implementation of the Charter at the barangay level improves service responsiveness and reduces transaction costs for citizens.

NPM also underscores accountability and transparency as essential elements of effective governance. Hood emphasizes that public organizations must be held accountable through clear performance targets and publicly accessible outcomes. The Citizens' Charter functions as a performance agreement between the government and its constituents, specifying deliverables, turnaround times, and complaint mechanisms (Behn, 2003). This framework allows for public scrutiny, which strengthens institutional accountability and reinforces trust in government services—an outcome this study aims to explore by assessing citizen perceptions at the frontline level.

Another important pillar of NPM is its client-centered approach. It reframes citizens not as passive recipients but as clients who deserve high-quality, efficient, and responsive public services. Lodge and Gill (2019) emphasize that contemporary public management increasingly focuses on user-centric service delivery, transparency, and accountability as mechanisms to build trust and improve citizen satisfaction. The Citizens' Charter embodies this principle by recognizing citizens' rights to prompt and efficient service. Through this framework, the study will examine whether service delivery at the barangay level reflects this client-orientation and how such responsiveness affects overall satisfaction of government performance.

Moreover, NPM emphasizes performance measurement as a critical management tool for evaluating and improving service delivery. Behn (2003) argues that measuring outcomes, not just inputs or processes, provides essential feedback for continuous improvement. This study leverages NPM's focus on

measurement by examining data from the Client Satisfaction Measurement (CSM) mandated by the Anti-Red Tape Authority (ARTA). Pursuant to Section 3(b), Rule IV of the Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) of RA 11032, the CSM captures citizen feedback on service standards set by the Charter—specifically timeliness, accessibility, simplicity, and overall satisfaction.

Ultimately, NPM not only guides the inquiry into how the Citizen’s Charter is implemented but also provides the analytical foundation for interpreting results. It informs the study’s impact by demonstrating how a citizen-focused, results-oriented public management framework can lead to practical recommendations for improving government performance, particularly at the barangay level where citizen interactions are most frequent and consequential.

Conceptual Framework of the Study

As shown in the conceptual flow of the study, the researcher will focus on determining the level of implementation and the level of client satisfaction in the service delivery, and the relationship between these two variables. The demographic profile of the client, including age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, employment status, monthly income, and service availed, serves as an input for this study. The demographic profile may influence both the implementation and client satisfaction. Additionally, the implementation may or may not affect client satisfaction.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Dr. Jose Rizal, the national hero of the Philippines, wrote an essay titled "La Indolencia de los Filipinos." (The Indolence of the Filipinos), which appeared in sections in the Journal of the La Solidaridad, the magazine published by the Propaganda Movement, initially detailed how cops in the government operated. Rizal describes the challenges Filipinos face when attempting to participate in business, as they are aware of,

"...how many documents, how many stamped papers, how much patience is needed to secure from the government a permit for enterprise. One must count upon the good will of this one, on the influence of that one, on a good bribe to another in order that the application be not pigeonholed, a present to the one further on so that he may pass it on to his chief; one must pray to God to give him good humor and time to see and examine it; to another, talent to recognize its expediency; to one further sufficient stupidity not to scent behind the enterprise an insurrectionary purpose...And above all, great patience, great knowledge of how to get along, plenty of money, a great deal of politics, many salutations, great influence, plenty of presents and complete resignation!" (Fores-Ganzon, G., 1996, translation of Rizal's La Solidaridad, 1890).

The widespread corruption and inefficiencies of Spanish governance were verified by the Americans who took over as the new colonial rulers. Jacobini and Associates (1956: 5) noted, citing the Philippine Commission report, that the Spanish government was "exploitative," that public works and road maintenance were "no more than the rudiments of a system of public education," that the Spanish government "did not even achieve the basic objective of good government in that it was not able to maintain peace and order," and that the Spanish government "did not sustain a satisfactory level in the administration of justice."

The Image of Philippine Bureaucracy

The perception of Philippine bureaucracy is unfavorable. The state's efficacy is compromised by entrenched bribery and corrupt practices, which also lead to widespread poverty, (Bernas 1996). The integrity of governmental institutions and, consequently, public trust are continually destroyed by such corrupt practices (Aniga 2014). As a result, those employed by the government are frequently and unjustly viewed as crooks, inefficient, corrupt, and slow to provide services (Brillantes and Fernandez 2011). Even worse, the public perceives the government as a whole to be indifferent to its demands. Citizens were conditioned to accept subpar government services as a result of the public's perception of the government (James 2011). The poor participation of citizens in public affairs and the innately complicated procedures in public offices, which slow down the processing of transactions in the government, are contributing factors to the issue getting worse.

This picture of Philippine bureaucracy prompted by former President Rodrigo R. Duterte reiterated his directives in simplifying government processes during the 2019 SONA, government and instrumentalities, including LGUs and the government corporations to simplify, he further added to fast-track LGU's processing of business permits, clearances "I am directing mayors and also the DILG Secretary Año: All clearances, permits, must be out at the very least within three days."

Reform Initiatives to Prevent Graft and Corruption

Several initiatives have been made to reduce corruption in the Philippine administration. Congress in the Philippines has passed numerous legislations aimed at combating corruption. For example, a whole article in the 1987 Philippine Constitution was devoted to providing guidelines for public servants and officials in the performance of their official duties (Bernas 1996). In the meantime, the standards of behavior that public servants should adhere to when carrying out their official duties are codified in Republic Act 6713, generally known as the Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards for Public Officials and Employees (Bernas 1996; Aranas 2016).

Numerous commissions, teams, and law enforcement agencies were also created to implement laws against corruption in the Philippines. Department Order No. 38-2016 created the Presidential Commission on Good Government (PCGG). Unfortunately, these attempts bear no substantial results due to: lack of political will on the part of the leader and agency assigned to implement conflicting laws on corruption, judicial inefficiency, low salaries of government employees, weak citizenship, absence of role model, punitive nature of anti-corrupt policies, and lack of reform priorities (Brillantes and Fernandez 2011; Carino and Alfiler 1986; Quah 2010; Reyes 1994). According to Carino and Alfiler (1986), majority of anti-corruption laws penalize rather than prevent the commission of corrupt acts. They argued that an effective anti-corruption measure must contain both a system of punishing offenders and a built-in mechanism for prevention coupled with public support at the agency level.

The reform initiative will bring about changes in the attitudes and behaviors of civil as well as servants in the public's perception of the provision of public services. This is so that the workers and supervisors may be held responsible to the performance requirements that are defined in the charter itself. Due to the fact that rewards and penalties are also based on these charters, the same citizen's charter will also encourage bureaucrats and government officials to act and behave in accordance with service standards. Residents as Additionally, "customers" have the authority to request appropriate services, make use of and offer feedback, and demand payment for subpar services. As a result, citizens who use public services are taking a more active role in determining how those services are delivered.

Good Governance

The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) defined governance as: "The exercise of political, economic and administrative authority in the management of the country's affairs at all levels. It comprises the mechanisms, processes and institutions through which citizens and groups articulate their interests, exercise their rights, meet their obligations and mediate their differences" (in UNDP-TUGI, 2003).

There are four aspects to this definition laid out by UNDP. One is that governance is broader concept than government. Power is recognized to exist even outside the formal institutions and authority in government. Second, that governance is more than just management, that it is also concerned with the governance environment in which management decisions are taken and implemented. Third, that governance emphasizes process arising from the complex relationship between different actors possessing

different interests. And lastly, that governance itself is a neutral concept, either positive or negative, thus necessitating a “good governance” that signifies an exercise of political, economic and administrative authority in the most positive, productive and creative form. The United Nations Development Program (UNDP) in the document *Governance for Sustainable Human Development* explains:

“Good governance is, among other things, participatory, transparent and accountable. It is also effective and equitable, and promotes the rule of law fairly. Good governance ensures that the voices of the poorest and the most vulnerable are based on broad consensus among key stakeholders – the state, the private sector and civil society” (in UNDP-TUGI 2003).”

Translating this good governance within the context of urban setting, The Urban Governance Initiative (TUGI) Users’ Manual spells out nine core characteristics of good urban governance: participation, rule of law, transparency, responsiveness, consensus orientation, equity, effectiveness and efficiency, accountability and strategic vision. It looked at participation as men and women having a voice in decision making, either directly or through legitimate intermediate institutions that represent their interests. It is built on freedom of association and speech, as well as capacities to participate constructively. It sees rule of law as legal frameworks that are fair and are enforced impartially, particularly the laws on human rights. It characterized transparency as building on free flow information, where processes, institutions and information are directly accessible to those concerned with them. Responsiveness is trying to serve all stakeholders. Consensus orientation is mediating different interests to reach broad consensus on what is the interest of the group, and where possible on policies and procedures. Equity pertains to availability of opportunities for all men and women to improve or maintain well-being. Effectiveness and efficiency refer to processes and institutions producing results that meet needs while making the best use of resources. It described accountability as answerability of decision makers in government, the private sector and civil society organizations to the public or institutional stakeholders. Strategic vision is broad and long term perspective on human development and its requirements. By and large, the term “governance” has by now become a more or less neutral concept that focuses on steering mechanisms in a certain political unit, emphasizing the interaction of state, business and society players. “Good Governance”, on the other hand, is not all neutral; rather it is a normative concept that again embodies a strong value judgment in favor of the retrenchment of the state, which is supposed to yield to business standard principles, and - not least-interests. In that sense, “Good governance” privileges the Second (business) over the First Sector (state), even in First Sector areas (Drechsler 2005, p.8). UNDP (1997) has defined Transparency as “sharing information, and acting in an open manner. It allows stakeholders to gather information that may be critical to uncovering abuses and defending their interests. Transparent systems have clear procedures for public decision making and open channels of communication between stakeholders and officials”. On the other hand, it discussed Accountability as a “requirement that officials answer to stakeholders on the disposal of their power and duties, act on criticisms or requirements made of them and accept responsibility in case of failure, incompetence. Accountability involves adhering to a set of established criteria and using these to measure the performance of officials and estimate economic and financial outputs. It requires the following pre-requisites: freedom of information, stakeholders who are able to organize; and rule of law”. The importance of stakeholder participation in formulating, implementing and institutionalizing policy is underscored in a lot of development planning and policy development literatures. Regardless of cultural or

geographic identities, citizen/community participation is considered an indispensable ingredient in a meaningful decision-making process. One of these literatures is the classic ladder of citizen participation and nonparticipation written by Sherry Arnstein (1971)¹ where she illustrated a ladder-like levels or modes where “have-not” citizens can have the opportunity to be involved in economic or political decision-making processes. It has eight rungs which starts at the bottom (nonparticipation) – manipulation, therapy, to informing, consultation, placation, partnership (tokenism), to delegated power, and citizen’s control which is the apex (citizen power) of the ladder. This simple typology however, does not capture the reality of varying degrees of influence the powerless/less powerful have in the entire decision-making process. Nonetheless, this serves to illustrate that there exist a construct where practitioners and students of citizen’s participation can look at to describe the levels of participation in development plans and projects. A variation of this typology is formulated by David Wilcox² (1994) wherein he modified the ladder into stances to read now as: Information; Consultation; Deciding together; Acting together and supporting independent community interests. Wilcox premises his typology that participation is a ‘controlled process’ wherein someone (with resources) initiates and manages the participation process and has a reason for doing so. He explains that Information stance is where you tell people what is planned; Consultation stance is where you offer a number of options and listen to the feedback you get; Deciding together stance is where you encourage others to provide some additional ideas and options, and join in deciding the best way forward; Acting together stance is where a partnership is forged to carry it out best decision; and Supporting independent community initiatives stance is where you help others do what they want - perhaps within a framework of grants, advice and support provided by the resource holder. Within the state sector itself, many of the principles of “Good Governance” are therefore identical with NPM. And while a unitary definition of the concept never existed, not even within the respective individual international finance institutions, “good” principles usually encompassed such concepts as transparency, efficiency, participation, responsibility, and market economy, state of law, democracy and justice. Many of them are indubitably “good” as such but all of them – except the last one, which is the most abstract – are heavily context dependent, hinging not only on definition and interpretation, but also on time and space (Drechsler 2005, p.8). The Citizen’s Charter is being viewed as an instrument to propagate and instill the values of accountability, transparency, participation, efficiency, and effectiveness in running the affairs of the local government and in implementing its projects and programs. These shall be used in expounding the formulation, implementation and institutionalization processes related to the citizen’s charter.

Citizen’s Charter

The concept of the Citizens’ Charter was first introduced in the United Kingdom in 1991 under Prime Minister John Major’s administration. This initiative aimed to enhance public service delivery by emphasizing transparency, accountability, and citizen-centered approaches (Drewry, 2005). The UK government set out to establish service standards and articulate the quality of service that citizens could expect from public institutions, intending to make public services more responsive to citizens’ needs. This framework included mechanisms for addressing grievances, allowing citizens to hold public institutions accountable for service quality. (Hood, 1991).

The importance of citizen’s charter is being recognized not just at governance levels (i.e. central-local; national-sub-national) sectoral level i.e. parent’s charter (schools), patient’s charter (hospital),

passenger's charter (rail) but also along approach/strategy level. A model of citizen's charter for disaster management is being advocated in hazard-prone Uttarakhand Region in India (Pande and Pande 2007). The Citizen's Charter of Disaster Management is considered to be another effective tool to bring in citizen-centric governance. Drewry in Pollitt (1998, pp349-350) points out that charters have been established across a range of countries, largely in response to the trans-national public administration reform agenda and its growing emphasis on the phenomenon known as the 'public sector consumer'. Andrisani, Hakim and Savas explain that citizens play different roles. One is as consumers of government services, and therefore government must, like all service providers, satisfy its customers. The citizen-consumer-customer is king. Customer's service is a major thrust of modern managers in government. This means getting things done right, quickly, courteously, and knowledgeably (2002, p9). One of the criticisms poised to citizen's charter is its name itself. More particular to the UK, the discourse centers on the semantics of the use of the terms citizens, customers, clients and users. Harrison (1999, p.58) for instance notes that placing of apostrophe in citizen's, patient's, parent's charters symbolizes the view of the individual with his or her own wants, needs, preferences and grievances which runs contrary to the view that citizens pertain to collective or group in relation to the state. Harrison points "mutual understanding between the state and the citizen cannot occur on an individual basis, but must be group to group". Another complication to this semantics is the question from whose view should the citizen's charter must emanate. Harrison (1999, p 58) says the local government is more inclined to see citizen within the group – the local community – possibly as a member of the electorate, and certainly someone who shares with the group civic rights which are additional to the rights of the consumer (the right to know, be heard, be treated with fairness, honesty and courtesy as well as the right to participate and be represented). The central government seems to view citizens differently in content and in purpose. Barnett and Harrison in Harrison (1999) explain: "there is clearly overlap, in that similar methods have been used for different aims. Thus, for example, decentralization can be consumer-based and initiated out of concern for more responsive service delivery, or can be citizen-based and concerned with the devolution of political power and increased participation". Users have responsibilities as well as rights (Harrison 1999). This cliché stems from the argument that citizen or client or customer's charter is a contract. Therefore, citizens, users or customers have the responsibility to make the contract work by fulfilling certain expectations as well like, showing the same courtesy to both service providers and other citizens, paying promptly and providing opinions and suggestions for service improvement. Harrison points the same expectation, for example by the Sheffield City Treasury, that customers in return should be honest, provide accurate and prompt information, pay bills and behave reasonably towards employees. The contract therefore is a "two-way street". The foregoing is consistent with an earlier observation and remark of Pollitt (1994, p.12) in the UK's citizen's charter conceptualization whereby citizens are viewed more as 'subjects' of the Crown and that the White Paper has no reference to citizens instead refers to users or consumers of public services. He explains "To be a consumer is to hold a particular position in a network of market relations. To be a citizen is to be a member of a political community, a richer concept embracing a much wider range of potential relationships". The UK example of charterism indicates that public sector consumerism is not solely concerned with the users of public services. It is fundamentally about service providers and the customer's awareness orientation of public service delivery agencies (Pollitt, 1998, p. 350). Lovell (1992) for his part argues that if the improvements in customer service required by the Citizen's Charter are to be effective and long lasting, changes in structures and systems will need to be accompanied

by change in culture and management style. A customer responsive culture is necessary if customer service is to be improved.

Citizen's Charter is a mutual agreement between citizen and service providers about the kind of services that a citizen can expect from the service providers which is considered as one of the most popular tools of New Public Management. Therefore, services provided through local government institutions are very vital. Managers/ personnel's must be held accountable and must show transparency in work and conduct because there are aspects of the job that can lead to misconception of the public interest, corruption and subversion (W. Raman 2018).

Since the Citizens' Charter concept has been adapted worldwide, it serves as a benchmark for improving public service delivery. The Philippines was inspired by this concept to combat bureaucratic red tape and promote a more service-oriented government through the implementation of the Citizens' Charter under RA 9485, also known as the Anti-Red Tape Act of 2007. This legislation mandates government agencies to create and publish a Citizens' Charter that outlines each agency's processes, service standards, and commitments to the public (Brillantes & Fernandez, 2011).

Citizens' Charter: A Tool for Enhancing Service Delivery

The Citizens' Charter initiative was introduced as part of the NPM reforms to provide citizens with clear and transparent information about the services they can expect from public organization. Citizens' Charter are designed to promote accountability, streamline procedures, and improve the responsiveness of government services. According to Bovaird and Loffler (2003), Charter help reduce bureaucratic inefficiencies by setting service standards and outlining the processes through which citizens can file complaints or seek redress when service fall short of expectations. According to Mendoza (2018), the implementation of Citizens' Charter helped reduce the processing time for services such as securing business permits and obtaining public documents. This improvement in efficiency directly contributed to higher levels of client satisfaction, as citizens experienced less bureaucratic red tape and delays.

A similar study by Alhambra et al. (2019) analyzed the effectiveness of the Citizen's Charter in reducing corruption and improving service delivery in local government units. Their findings showed that government agencies that adhered strictly to the standards outlined in their Charters experienced higher satisfaction ratings from citizens. The Charter also serve as tools for promoting transparency and accountability, key components of the NPM framework.

The Anti-Red Tape Act of 2007

The Anti-Red Tape Act of 2007 is both punitive and preventive in nature which solicited citizens' support in terms of feedback and is implemented at the agency level. The philosophy behind the law is to inform citizens of the kind and quality of services they deserve. It is the only anti-corruption legislation based on client's perception of what efficient government should be and of how services should be

delivered. It is intended to improve efficiency in the delivery of government services to the public by reducing bureaucratic red tape, preventing graft and corruption and providing penalties therefor.

The primary objective of the act is to promote integrity, accountability, prevent graft and corruption in the bureaucracy, instill transparency, and increase public accountability of government officials. It has three core components: (a) Citizen's Charter (Section 6), (b) Assurance to the citizens of their right and access to frontline services and the details that must be observed by government officials in the execution of their functions (Section 8), and (c) Use of Report Card Survey. The first core component, the Citizen's Charter (CC) is a benchmark of performance as it serves as a social contract with the citizens regarding the manner and time necessary for a government agency to deliver a particular service. Not only does it promote effective and efficient delivery of services in the government but also promote transparency while imposing upon accountability among public officials in the performance of their duties. According to Carino, the strength of CC is that it informs citizens of the benchmark of performance so that they may demand for it (Carino and Alfiler 1986). The Act defines Citizens' Charter as:

“an official document, a service standard, or a pledge that communicates in simple terms, information on the services provided by the government to its citizens. It describes in detail the comprehensive and uniform checklist of requirements for each type of application or request (RA 11032)

According to Calina (2015), Citizen's Charter treats citizens as citizen-consumers since it is propagated under the New Public Administration Model. The idea is to replace consumer rights for political and legal rights. The citizens are considered consumers of government services hence should be the ultimate judge on the quality of services provided by the public institutions. The second core component is its assurance to the citizens of their right and access to frontline services and the details that must be observed by government officials in the execution of their functions (Section 8). It includes the requirements as to the acceptance and denial of a request for government service, the person-in-charge, and the period within which the request must be acted upon including the appropriate explanation why a citizen cannot avail of certain service. And to ensure observance, a complaint desk is designated in every government agency. The last core component is the use of Report Card Survey to monitor the implementation, formulation, and observance of the requirements and standard of services that the government may deliver to its citizens. The purpose of this is to prevent red tape and obtain feedback on the implementation of the act using the perspective of public clients and service benchmark set by the Philippine Civil Service Commission.

The implementation of the Barangay Citizen's Charter in the Philippines has been pivotal in enhancing the efficiency and transparency of local government services. Mendoza (2016) highlights that initiatives like the Anti-Red Tape Act (ARTA) of 2007 aim to reduce bureaucratic inefficiencies by standardizing procedures and promoting transparency. Such measures ensure that citizens have clear information on service requirements, procedures, and fees, thereby minimizing confusion and fostering trust in local governance.

Further emphasizing the importance of standardized service delivery, Villanueva (2022), underscores that clear guidelines and procedures contribute significantly to reducing inefficiencies and improving

accessibility for stakeholders. This aligns with the principles of the New Public Management (NPM) model, which advocates for a customer-centric approach in public service delivery.

Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018

Republic Act No. 11032 is an act that aims to streamline the current systems and procedures of government services. It is the landmark law of the Duterte administration that addresses priority number 3 of its 0+10 Point Socio-economic Agenda. This particular agenda pertains to improving the competitiveness of and ease of doing business in the Philippines. Signed into law on 28 May 2018, the law effectively amends Republic Act 9485 or the Anti-Red Tape Act of 2007. The strengthened version of the law is poised to facilitate prompt actions or resolution of all government transactions with efficiency. It applies to all government offices and agencies in the Executive Department including local government units (LGUs), government-owned or -controlled corporations, and other government instrumentalities, located in the Philippines or abroad, that provide services covering business-related and non-business transactions as defined in the implementing rules and regulations.

Client Satisfaction in Public Service Delivery

Client satisfaction has become a central measure of success in public service delivery, particularly as governments worldwide strive to become more responsive and efficient. According to Oliver (1980), client satisfaction is a psychological outcome that results from the comparison between clients' expectations and their perceptions of the actual service received. While this concept originated in the private sector, it has been widely adapted to measure satisfaction in public services, where meeting citizen expectations is increasingly tied to governance reforms and service quality standards.

New Public Management and its Influence on Client Satisfaction

The emergence of New Public Management (NPM) has reshaped public sector practices globally, NPM reforms emphasize efficiency, decentralization, competition, and a client-oriented approach, borrowing heavily from private sector management models (Hood, 1991). NPM advocates for governments to adopt business-like practices to improve service delivery and customer satisfaction. One of the key components of NPM is the focus on accountability and transparency, which aligns with the introduction of the Citizens' Charter across many nations.

NPM-driven reforms have significantly impacted client satisfaction in countries where these practices have been institutionalized. The studies by Pollitt and Bouckaert (2011) highlight that countries like the UK, New Zealand, and Australia, which implemented NPM reforms early, have seen improvements in service quality and increased citizen satisfaction. The reforms encourage public organizations to become more competitive, efficient, and focused on client needs, transforming traditional bureaucratic models into service-oriented entities. In this context, the Citizens' Charter functions as tool for institutionalizing NPM principles by establishing performance standards and increasing accountability to the public.

Challenges in Measuring Client Satisfaction in Public Service

Despite the increased focus on client satisfaction in public services, measuring it remains a challenge due to the diverse nature of public service recipients and the complexity of services offered. Loffler and Bovaird (2004), argue that public services cater to a heterogeneous population with varying needs and expectations, making it difficult to develop a one-size-fits-all approach to measuring satisfaction. Unlike the private sector, where satisfaction is often tied to consumer choice and market dynamics, public services are influenced by broader socio-political factors, such as legal frameworks, public accountability, and equity.

Furthermore, client satisfaction is only one indicator of service performance. In the study of George and Pandey (2017), highlights the importance of considering other factors, such as service accessibility, fairness, and responsiveness, when evaluating public service delivery. They argue that while Citizens' Charter helps improve service quality and client satisfaction, other contextual factors like political stability, governance structures, and resource availability must also be considered.

Anchored in the principles of New Public Management (NPM), this study recognizes the emphasis on efficiency, accountability, and performance measurement in public service delivery. NPM advocates for treating citizens as clients and promotes the use of tools, such as performance indicators, service standards, and output-based management, to ensure high-quality and timely service provision (Pollitt & Bouckaert, 2011). In line with this, the Citizens' Charter serves as a mechanism to institutionalize client satisfaction by clarifying service commitments and enhancing transparency (Bovaird & Löffler, 2009). Joshi and Houtzager (2012) add that Charters function both as instruments for improving service delivery and as platforms for citizens to hold governments accountable. Building on this, Osborne, Radnor, and Nasi (2013) emphasize that public service value is co-created between providers and clients, shifting the focus from mere outputs to the perceived value and experience of service users.

Service Delivery and Public Sectors Reforms in the Philippines

Service delivery reforms in the Philippines have mirrored these global movements. Atienza (2020) noted that the decentralization efforts improved service delivery in some areas but revealed inconsistencies, suggesting that client satisfaction often depended on the capacity and political will of local government units. Brillantes and Fernandez (2011) emphasized the historical trust deficits in the Philippine public sector, explaining that Citizens' Charters were introduced to rebuild trust by formalizing citizen expectations. Meanwhile, Mendoza (2017) and Mendoza and Acheron (2016) stressed that citizen participation is essential, arguing that Citizens' Charters should not only standardize services but also empower citizens to actively monitor government performance. Tapales (2015) and Tapales and Villamil (2017) found that local governments that genuinely implemented the Citizens' Charter experienced improved client satisfaction, whereas those treating it as a compliance exercise did not. Similarly, Reyes, Tigno, and Cabaero (2019) documented the Charter's role as a corrective mechanism designed to address bureaucratic inefficiencies and dissatisfaction.

Several studies have directly assessed Citizens' Charter implementation within local government units at the barangay level. Cordez San Jose (2023), in Camarines Sur's 4th District, found that although LGUs generally complied with Charter-mandated visibility and content requirements, frontline users often remained unaware of its provisions, and unclear procedures still hindered efficient service delivery. In Pampanga, Casimiro et al. (2024) reported that two barangays demonstrated strong transparency and accountability in Charter implementation—citizens felt well-informed about ordinances, infrastructure planning, and grievance-handling processes. Gonzales and Rivera (2019) noted that while formal compliance with Charters was high, actual service quality, especially staff behavior, had a stronger impact on citizen satisfaction. Santos (2020) emphasized that transparency provisions like grievance redress systems in Charters were linked to lower perceived corruption. However, Villanueva (2022) warned that without deeper cultural change, Citizens' Charters risk becoming mere paper exercises rather than genuine reform tools.

Demographic Factor in Client Satisfaction

The role of demographic factors in client satisfaction has been extensively examined. Buazon, Santos, and De Guzman (2003) found that older, better-educated, and higher-income citizens tended to report higher satisfaction with government services, possibly due to greater familiarity with bureaucratic processes. Almonte and Roxas (2021) similarly indicated that individuals with higher education and income levels had heightened expectations, which often resulted in more critical evaluations of public services. Sta. Maria and Lapuz (2020) observed that marital status influenced satisfaction levels, with married clients particularly valuing the timeliness and courtesy of service delivery. Cabildo and Aquino (2022) emphasized that those with college-level education were more demanding and scrutinized government services more closely. Soriano and Dizon (2021) concluded that higher educational attainment was linked not only to higher expectations but also to a greater propensity for filing formal complaints when dissatisfied.

Socio-economic status and employment factors were also shown to influence perceptions of service delivery. Cammayo (2023) reported that unemployed citizens often perceived government services as slow and discriminatory, resulting in lower satisfaction levels. Canta and Calisin (2021) found that low-income groups typically faced longer waiting times and less access to redress mechanisms. Mangahas (2020) suggested that wealthier citizens often navigated government systems more effectively, leading to higher satisfaction rates.

Civic engagement and the availability of feedback mechanisms were also identified as critical determinants of satisfaction. Aquino (2021) demonstrated that citizens who actively participated in governance processes reported greater satisfaction with services, indicating that a sense of ownership improves client perceptions. Abenoja (2013) emphasized the importance of accessible feedback mechanisms within Citizens' Charters, finding that satisfaction levels increased when grievance systems were present and responsive. Reyes and Dela Cruz (2021) similarly observed that effective complaint systems under the Citizens' Charter framework improved perceptions of government responsiveness and trustworthiness.

Beyond the Philippine context, international studies further illuminate the relationship between service standards and client satisfaction. The World Bank (2018) found that clearly articulated performance standards in education and other sectors enhanced citizen trust. Albrecht and Brewer (2016) stressed that services perceived as simple, timely, and understandable were more likely to satisfy clients. Grindle (2017) highlighted that micro-level bureaucratic reforms, such as service commitments, could reshape broader perceptions of governance legitimacy. Van de Walle and Scott (2011) similarly concluded that citizens' daily service experiences were crucial in building trust in government institutions.

Despite the potential of Citizens' Charters, challenges to their effective implementation persist. Mendoza and Torres (2018) identified patronage politics and weak enforcement mechanisms as major obstacles to realizing the full potential of New Public Management reforms like Citizens' Charters. David, Pizarro, and Ballada (2020) noted that leadership commitment and sustained citizen vigilance are essential for maintaining the integrity of service reforms. Manasan (2016) warned that without continuous monitoring and real citizen engagement, reforms could become symbolic rather than substantive. Finally, Lledo and Abinales (2019) underscored the need to manage citizen expectations carefully through strategic communication to avoid frustration and cynicism when implementing service delivery reforms.

Synthesis

The implementation of the Citizens' Charter, under the provisions of RA 11032, is critical in enhancing client satisfaction within public service delivery. The law mandates that government institutions adhere to standardized service processes, transparency, and promptness in handling public transactions, aimed at reducing bureaucratic inefficiencies. Implementation of the charter focuses on improving government responsiveness through clear guidelines and expectations for service delivery, fostering greater accountability and reducing red tape.

Client satisfaction, in this context, is measured by how well these services meet citizens' expectations, which are increasingly shaped by principles of New Public Management. The NPM-inspired reforms push for a more client-oriented approach, demanding not only efficient but also transparent and equitable service delivery. However, the effectiveness of the Citizens' Charter implementation and its impact on client satisfaction depend on several factors such as resource allocation, capability and the broader political and institutional framework within which services are delivered.

Challenges arise in meeting the diverse needs of citizens, as public services must cater to various socio-economic backgrounds, making a one-size-fits-all approach difficult. While the Citizens' Charter sets the groundwork for standardizing service performance, the real measure of success lies in the consistent application of these standards ensuring that all clients receive fair, timely, and accessible services. Therefore, assessing both implementation and client satisfaction becomes essential in understanding how effectively RA 11032 drives improvements in public service delivery.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research approach, utilizing a combination of descriptive, comparative, and correlational designs. A descriptive comparative design was utilized to determine if there was a significant difference in the level of implementation of the Citizen's Charter of the Barangay and the level of client satisfaction when they were grouped according to their demographic profile. Meanwhile, the descriptive correlational design was used to determine the relationship between the level of implementation of the Citizens' Charter and level of client satisfaction.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted across the 30 barangays of Naic, Cavite, located in the western part of the province along the shorelines of Manila Bay. It is a first-class municipality with a population of approximately 160,987 residents, according to the 2020 population census of the Philippine Statistics Authority.

Participants of the Study

The participants were composed of clients who had transactions and availed of services in the barangays. A total of 450 participants, or 15 from each barangay, were selected to participate in the study.

Sampling Technique

This study employed a purposive quota sampling technique to ensure both relevance and equitable representation among participants. Purposive sampling was applied to select participants who had availed of services in their respective barangays, as these participants possessed direct experience relevant to the study's objectives. Simultaneously, quota sampling was utilized to guarantee proportional representation by a fixed number of 15 qualified participants selected from each barangay, resulting in a total sample size of 450 participants.

The selection process was conducted after the participants completed their transactions at the barangay. This approach ensured that all participants had recent and relevant exposure to the barangay services.

Data Gathering Procedure

In data gathering, the research employed a descriptive, comparative, and correlational design. The study collected information on the clients' demographic profiles, the level of implementation of the Citizen's Charter, and level of client satisfaction with the service delivery. The following steps were undertaken:

The researcher secured an approved letter addressed from the Local Chief Executive of the Municipality of Naic, seeking permission to conduct the study. Afterwards, a questionnaire was administered using printed survey forms to clients who had transactions and availed themselves of barangay services after their transactions. The researcher immediately checked for possible errors or misinformation in the responses.

Research Instrument

The researcher primarily used a printed survey questionnaire as the main tool for gathering data for the study. The research instrument was a self-developed survey questionnaire based on Reference B, the Citizen’s Charter Handbook Template provided by ARTA, to assess the level of implementation of the Citizen’s Charter. In addition, a self-developed question was included to measure the customer service indicator of client satisfaction, and the Harmonized Client Satisfaction Measurement (CSM) tool from ARTA was adapted to assess the quality of service in the overall level of client satisfaction with the New Public Management principle.

The survey questionnaire was divided into three parts:

Part 1 included demographic information about the client, such as their barangay, age, sex, educational attainment, civil status, employment status, monthly income, and service availed.

Part 2 assessed the level of implementation of the Citizen’s Charter, focusing on aspects such as the uniform/standard requirements, procedures for obtaining specific services, documents required by clients, fees involved, and the procedure for filing complaints. The mean value was verbally interpreted according to the implementation as observed by the client and was analyzed using the following scale:

Table 1. **Rating for the level of implementation of the citizen’s charter**

Adjectival Rating	Range	Qualitative Interpretation
Strongly Agree	4.50 – 5.00	Fully Implemented. The CC is completely executed with no significant issues.
Agree	3.50 – 4.49	Implemented. The CC is executed but may have minor areas for improvement.
Moderately Agree or Disagree	2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Implemented. The CC is executed in essential areas but lacks consistency or thoroughness.
	1.50 – 2.49	Partially Implemented. The CC is incomplete or inadequately executed, requiring considerable improvements.
Strongly Disagree	1.00 – 1.49	Not Implemented. The CC has not been executed at all and requires immediate attention.

Part 3 measured the level of client satisfaction with the service delivery in the barangay based on the Citizen’s Charter, focusing on aspects such as customer service and service quality. The mean value was verbally interpreted according to the satisfaction of the clients and was analyzed using the following scale:

Table 2. Rating for the level of satisfaction

Adjectival Rating	Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
Strongly Agree	4.50 – 5.00	Highly Satisfied. Participant express a high level of satisfaction, indicating excellent performance or experience.
Agree	3.50 – 4.49	Very Satisfied. Participant are satisfied, showing good performance or experience, but with minor areas for improvement.
Moderately Agree or Disagree	2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Satisfied. Participant are indecisive or uncertain, suggesting average performance or experience without strong positive or negative views
Disagree	1.50 – 2.49	Dissatisfied. Participant indicate dissatisfaction, pointing to below-average performance or experience.
Strongly Disagree	1.00 – 1.49	Very Dissatisfied. Participant express strong level of dissatisfaction, signalling poor performance or experience that requires immediate attention.

Validation of the Instrument

The research instrument underwent a rigorous validation process to ensure its reliability and validity in measuring the level of implementation and level of client satisfaction in the service delivery according to the Citizen’s Charter of RA 11032.

Firstly, the content validity of the questionnaire was established by subjecting it to scrutiny by two members of the academe: one from the Department of Social Sciences in CAS and another from the Arts and Sciences Department in CvSU Naic. Furthermore, two representatives from the DILG: one from the National Barangay Operation Office (NBOO) and another from DILG Naic, also evaluated the instrument. Their inputs ensured that the questionnaire comprehensively covered all the variables of the study. Additionally, the instrument was reviewed by an accredited English-Filipino language critic from CELLAR to ensure the proper use of language, clarity of questions, and appropriateness of translation for both English and Filipino versions of the questionnaire.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools and procedures were used to describe the data in the study:

Frequency and Percentage were used to describe the demographic profile of the clients.

Median was used to determine the level of implementation and the level of client satisfaction.

Kruskal-Wallis test (One-way ANOVA) and Mann-Whitney U test were used to analyze whether there was a significant difference among the indicators of the implementation and client satisfaction based on the demographic profile of the clients.

Friedman Two-way ANOVA and Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test were used to compare the indicators of implementation and client satisfaction.

Spearman Rank was used to determine whether there is a significant relationship between the implementation and client satisfaction.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher ensured the protection of participants' rights and the integrity of the research process in accordance with the Data Privacy Act. First and foremost, informed consent was distributed and collected from all participants prior to their involvement in the study. Participants were fully informed about the purpose of the research, the procedures involved, potential risks and benefits, and their right to withdraw from the study at any time without consequences.

Confidentiality was strictly maintained throughout the data collection and analysis phases. Personal information and responses collected from the participants were kept confidential and stored securely. Participants were not identified individually in any reports or publications arising from the study, and data were presented in aggregate form to protect their privacy.

Additionally, the study complied with relevant ethical guidelines and regulations, including those set forth by the university ethics review board and the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The researcher continually reflected on ethical issues throughout the research process, seeking guidance and making adjustments as needed to uphold ethical standards and promote trustworthiness in the study's outcomes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of Clients

In Table 3, the demographic profile provides an overview of the client's characteristics based on age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, employment status, monthly income, and services availed.

Table 3. Distribution of clients according to demographic profile

Demographic Profile	Classification	Participant/Client	
		FREQUENCY (N=450)	PERCENT
Age	18 to 24	82	18
	25 to 34	142	32
	35 to 44	123	27
	45 to 54	71	16
	55 and above	32	7
Sex	Male	201	45
	Female	249	55
Civil Status	Single	185	41
	Married	219	49
	Widow	24	5
	Separated	22	5
Educational Attainment	No Formal Education	16	4
	Elementary/High School	174	39
	College	232	52
	Post Graduate	28	6
Employment Status	Employed	217	48
	Self-Employed	80	18
	Unemployed	96	21
	Non-Working	57	13
Monthly Income	No Income	112	25
	21,194 and below	287	64
	21,195 to 43,828	43	10
	43,829 and above	8	2
Service Availed	Brgy. Clearance/Certificate	387	86
	Business Clearance/Certificate	49	11
	Brgy. Facilities	11	2
	Blotter	3	1

Age

The largest portion of barangay clients, 32 percent, belong to the 25 to 34 age group, followed by those aged 35 to 44 with 27 percent. A smaller proportion falls within the 45 to 54 age bracket with 16 percent, while the youngest group, aged 18 to 24, accounts for 18 percent. The least represented category consists of individuals aged 55 and above, making up only seven percent of the total.

Sex

The barangay clients are almost evenly distributed between males and females, with a slight majority being female at 55 percent compared to male participants at 45 percent.

Civil Status

Nearly half of the barangay clients, 49 percent, are married, while 41 percent are single. A smaller percentage are widow at 5 percent and separated at 5 percent.

Educational Attainment

More than half of the barangay clients, 52 percent, have attained a college education, while thirty-nine percent have completed elementary or high school. A small percentage, 6 percent, have pursued postgraduate studies, whereas 4 percent have no formal education.

Employment Status

Almost half of the barangay clients, 48 percent, were employed, while 18 percent were self-employed. A notable portion, 21 percent, is unemployed, and 13 percent fall under the non-working category.

Monthly Income

A significant portion of barangay clients, 64 percent, earn 21,194 or below per month. Meanwhile, 25 percent have no income, while 10 percent earn 21,195 to 43,828. A very small percentage, 2 percent, belongs to the highest income bracket, earning between 43,829 and 219,140.

Services Availed

The most commonly availed service is the Barangay Clearance or Certificate, accounting for 86 percent of total transactions. Business Clearance or Certificate follows at 11 percent, while only a small percentage availed of barangay facilities at 2 percent and blotter services at 1 percent.

Level of Implementation of the Citizens' Charter Provision of RA 11032

In Table 4, the findings on the level of implementation of the Barangay Citizen's Charter reveal a strong adherence to the prescribed standards for service delivery, as indicated by the consistent median rating of 4.00, which can be interpreted as implemented across all indicators. The results suggest that the Citizens' Charter is established and effectively executed at the barangay level.

Table 4. Level of Implementation of the Citizens' Charter

Indicator	Median	Verbal Interpretation
Uniform/Standard Requirements		
1. The Barangay Citizen Charter is posted at the main entrance of offices or at the most conspicuous place.	4.00	Implemented
2. The Barangay Citizen Charter is posted in the form of published materials written either English or Filipino.	4.00	Implemented
3. The Barangay Citizen Charter enumerates the comprehensive checklist of requirements needed for each type of request.	4.00	Implemented
4. The Barangay Citizen Charter enumerates the uniform checklist of requirements needed for each type of request.	4.00	Implemented
5. The Barangay Citizen Charter enumerates the step-by-step procedure to obtain a particular service.	4.00	Implemented
6. The Barangay Citizen Charter determines the person responsible at each step.	4.00	Implemented
7. The Barangay Citizen Charter determine the maximum time to conclude the process.	4.00	Implemented
8. The Barangay Citizen Charter enumerates the documents to be presented by the requesting party if necessary.	4.00	Implemented
9. The Barangay Citizen Charter determines the amount of fees needed if necessary.	4.00	Implemented
10. The Barangay Citizen Charter determines the procedure of filing a complaint.	4.00	Implemented
Median	4.00	Implemented
Procedure to Obtain a Particular Service		
1. The steps needed to obtain the service are clearly explained.	4.00	Implemented
2. The list of required documents and forms for the service is easy to understand.	4.00	Implemented
3. The steps in the procedure were carried out in a timely manner.	4.00	Implemented
4. The information on the service procedure is easily accessible.	4.00	Implemented
5. The fees and costs involved in the procedures are clearly explained and transparent.	4.00	Implemented
Median	4.00	Implemented
Person/s Responsible for Each Step		

1. The person/s responsible for each step in the Citizen’s Charter process are clearly identified and easy to locate.	4.00	Implemented
2. The person/s responsible for each step demonstrates the necessary skills and knowledge to perform their duties effectively.	4.00	Implemented
3. The person/s responsible for each step takes full accountability for the tasks they are assigned.	4.00	Implemented
4. The person/s responsible for each step act promptly and in a timely manner.	4.00	Implemented
5. The person/s responsible for each step are effective and maintains clear, efficient communication with the public.	4.00	Implemented
Median	4.00	Implemented
Maximum Time to Conclude the Process		
1. The process was completed within the maximum time frame stated in the Citizen’s Charter.	4.00	Implemented
2. The process was carried out efficiently and did not experience unnecessary delays.	4.00	Implemented
3. The maximum time frame outlined in the Citizen’s Charter is reasonable for completing the process.	4.00	Implemented
Median	4.00	Implemented
Document/s to be Presented by the Client		
1. The information provided about the required documents is clear and easy to understand.	4.00	Implemented
2. The list of required documents is complete and covers all necessary information.	4.00	Implemented
3. The legal basis or justification for each required document is clearly explained.	4.00	Implemented
4. The documents required are reasonable and not unnecessarily burdensome.	4.00	Implemented
5. The total number of documents required to be presented is reasonable.	4.00	Implemented
6. The required documents are relevant and appropriate for the process.	4.00	Implemented
Median	4.00	Implemented
Amount of Fees		
1. The fees being collected has a clear legal basis and are in accordance with the applicable regulations.	4.00	Implemented
2. Sufficient information about the fees to be collected is provided upfront, including any breakdowns if applicable.	4.00	Implemented

3. The terms and mode of payment for the fees are affordable and manageable.	4.00	Implemented
4. The amount of fees being charged is reasonable and appropriate to the service or request being processed.	4.00	Implemented
5. The fees collected are directly relevant to the service or request, with no unnecessary or unrelated charges.	4.00	Implemented
Median	4.00	Implemented
Procedure for Filing Complaints		
1. The procedure for filing a complaint is clear and easy to understand.	4.00	Implemented
2. The steps involved in filing a complaint are appropriate and suitable for addressing the issue.	4.00	Implemented
3. The procedure accurately reflects the correct steps required to file a complaint.	4.00	Implemented
4. The steps in the complaint filing process are presented in a logical and easy-to-follow sequence.	4.00	Implemented
5. The time indicated for each step in the complaint process is realistic and efficiently observed.	4.00	Implemented
6. The complete process flow for filing a complaint, including all steps and requirements, is clearly provided.	4.00	Implemented
Median	4.00	Implemented
Overall Median	4.00	Implemented

Legend:

<i>1.00 – 1.49</i>	<i>Not Implemented</i>
<i>1.50 – 2.49</i>	<i>Partially Implemented</i>
<i>2.50 – 3.49</i>	<i>Moderately Implemented</i>
<i>3.50 – 4.49</i>	<i>Implemented</i>
<i>4.50 – 5.00</i>	<i>Fully Implemented</i>

The results show that the Charter is properly posted in conspicuous locations, clearly written in English or Filipino, and includes a comprehensive checklist of requirements, step-by-step procedures, designated staff, maximum processing time, and complaint mechanisms. The procedural steps for obtaining services are well-defined, accessible, and carried out efficiently, ensuring smooth transactions for citizens.

Furthermore, the accountability of staff is evident, as staff responsible for each step of the service process are easily identifiable and demonstrate competence, efficiency, and responsiveness in their duties. The prescribed maximum processing time is consistently met, minimizing unnecessary delays. The required documents for availing services are reasonable, justified, and relevant, ensuring that compliance requirements are neither excessive nor burdensome. Transparency in fees is also upheld, as the study confirms that charges are aligned with legal provisions, disclosed upfront, and deemed appropriate for the services rendered. Lastly, the complaint filing mechanism is structured, easy to understand, and efficiently communicated, allowing for an organized approach to addressing grievances.

Overall, the implementation of the Citizens' Charter in barangays reflects a well-integrated practice that upholds efficiency, accountability, and transparency in service delivery.

Level of Implementation in terms of uniform/standard requirements

The presence of uniform and standard requirements ensures transparency and accessibility, as the Citizens' Charter is publicly posted and provides a clear and comprehensive checklist of procedures, requirements, and fees. This structured approach minimizes confusion and helps standardize service delivery.

A similar study has shown that publicly posted service guidelines, standardized procedures, and clear service timelines contribute to reducing bureaucratic inefficiencies and improving accessibility for citizens (Reyes & Dela Cruz, 2021; Santos, 2020). Studies also emphasize that minimizing bureaucratic red tape and ensuring fairness in service transactions are key drivers of positive perceptions toward local government services, reflecting the customer-centric model of NPM (Mendoza & Torres, 2018; Villanueva, 2022).

Level of Implementation in terms of the procedure to obtain a particular service

The procedure for obtaining a particular service is also effectively implemented, with participants affirming that the steps are clearly explained, accessible, and carried out in a timely manner. This suggests that barangay staff successfully communicate service requirements, reducing inefficiencies and delays.

Level of Implementation in terms of person/s responsible for each step

The staff responsible for each step is well-identified, competent, and accountable, ensuring smooth service transactions. Their responsiveness and knowledge contribute to effective service provision and public trust.

Level of Implementation in terms of the maximum time to conclude the process

In terms of processing time, the findings confirm that services are completed within the maximum time frame specified in the Citizen's Charter. The absence of unnecessary delays reflects the barangay's commitment to efficiency, which aligns with the principles of New Public Management (NPM) by emphasizing streamlined procedures and improved service delivery.

Level of Implementation in terms of document/s to be presented by the client

Clarity in document requirements is another strong aspect of the Citizen's Charter implementation. The list of required documents is complete and provides all necessary information. Legal justifications for each requirement are clearly explained, ensuring transparency. Additionally, the number of documents

required is reasonable and not unduly burdensome, making the process more accessible for citizens. The relevance and appropriateness of the required documents further reflect to the service delivery.

Level of Implementation in terms of the amount of fees

The study also finds that the collection of fees is transparent, legally grounded, and reasonable, reinforcing fairness and compliance with existing regulations. Payment terms and modes are deemed manageable and affordable, while the amount charged is considered reasonable in relation to the services provided. The absence of unnecessary charges reinforces public trust in the fairness of the process.

Level of Implementation in terms of the procedure for filing complaints

The Citizen’s Charter provides a clear and easy-to-understand procedure for filing complaints. The steps involved are logically sequenced and appropriate for addressing concerns. The process accurately reflects the correct steps required to file a complaint, and the time allocated for each step is realistic and efficiently observed. A comprehensive process flow is provided, ensuring that complainants are well-informed about the necessary actions to take.

Overall, the uniform "Implemented" rating across all areas suggests that the Barangay Citizen’s Charter is functioning effectively to enhance transparency, efficiency, and accountability in local service delivery. The findings on the implementation of the Barangay Citizen’s Charter align with previous studies indicating that adherence to prescribed service delivery standards enhances transparency, accountability, and efficiency in local government operations. Rooted in the principles of New Public Management (NPM), which advocate for performance-driven governance, streamlined processes, and customer-oriented service, the effective implementation of the Citizen’s Charter reflects a shift toward a more responsive and results-based public administration (Hood, 1991; Pollitt & Bouckaert, 2017).

Level of client satisfaction in the service delivery

In Table 5, the findings on client satisfaction in service delivery indicate a consistently high level of satisfaction across all assessed indicators, with an overall median rating of 4.00, which can be interpreted as satisfied. This suggests that the barangay's service delivery meets client expectations in terms of customer service and quality of service.

Table 5. Level of client satisfaction

Indicator	Median	Verbal Interpretation
Customer Service		
1.The staff was friendly and courteous in assisting me with my concerns.	4.00	Satisfied
2. The staff responded to my inquiries promptly.	4.00	Satisfied
3. The staff demonstrated professionalism in addressing my concerns.	4.00	Satisfied

4. The staff was knowledgeable and competent in handling my request or issue.	4.00	Satisfied
5. The information provided by the staff was clear and easy to understand.	4.00	Satisfied
6. The staff showed a genuine willingness to help resolve my concern.	4.00	Satisfied
7. The staff resolved my issue or handled my request within a reasonable timeframe.	4.00	Satisfied
	4.00	Satisfied
Median		
Quality of Service		
1. I am satisfied with the service that I availed.	4.00	Satisfied
2. I spent a reasonable amount of time for my transaction.	4.00	Satisfied
3. The office followed the transaction's requirements and steps based on the information provided.	4.00	Satisfied
4. The steps I needed to do for my transaction were easy and simple.	4.00	Satisfied
5. I easily found information about my transaction from the office or its website.	4.00	Satisfied
6. I paid a reasonable amount of fees for my transaction.	4.00	Satisfied
7. I feel the office was fair to everyone, or "walang palakasan", during my transaction.	4.00	Satisfied
8. I was treated courteously by the staff, and (if asked for help) the staff was helpful.	4.00	Satisfied
9. I got what I needed from the government office, or (if denied) denial of request was sufficiently explained to me.	4.00	Satisfied
Median	4.00	Satisfied
Overall Median	4.00	Satisfied

Legend:

<i>1.00 – 1.49</i>	<i>Very Dissatisfied</i>
<i>1.50 – 2.49</i>	<i>Dissatisfied</i>
<i>2.50 – 3.49</i>	<i>Neutral</i>
<i>3.50 – 4.49</i>	<i>Satisfied</i>
<i>4.50 – 5.00</i>	<i>Very Satisfied</i>

The high levels of client satisfaction observed in the study are consistent with previous research on the implementation of the Citizens' Charter in local government units. Studies have shown that adherence to clearly defined service standards, transparent procedures, and responsive personnel significantly enhances public trust and service quality perceptions (Reyes & Dela Cruz, 2021; Santos, 2020).

Level of client satisfaction in terms of customer service

Clients expressed satisfaction with the friendliness, courtesy, and professionalism of the staff. The ability of the staff to respond promptly to inquiries, provide clear and understandable information, and demonstrate competence in handling requests reflects an efficient and citizen-oriented approach. The willingness of staff to assist and resolve concerns within a reasonable timeframe further enhances the positive perception of service delivery. These findings highlight the service-oriented staff in improving the overall experience of clients.

Level of client satisfaction in terms of quality of service

The results for quality of service also indicate a high level of satisfaction, particularly in the efficiency, fairness, and transparency of transactions. Clients found the transaction steps easy to follow and were able to complete their requests within a reasonable time. The adherence of the barangay to prescribed procedures, availability of transaction-related information, and reasonable fees contributed to a smooth service experience. Additionally, the perception of fairness in processing transactions, as reflected in the response that there was no preferential treatment, reinforces trust in the integrity of barangay service.

Overall, the consistently high satisfaction ratings suggest that the barangay has successfully implemented citizen-friendly service practices. This aligns with the principles of New Public Management (NPM), which emphasize efficiency, responsiveness, and customer-oriented governance.

Difference in the level of implementation when grouped according to age

In Table 6, the results indicate significant differences in the level of implementation of the Citizen's Charter across different age groups, as confirmed by the Kruskal-Wallis test, $p = 0.000$ for all indicators. Clients aged 55 and above consistently reported the highest mean ranks, indicating a more favorable level of implementation. In contrast, the 35 to 44 age group showed the lowest mean ranks, while the 18 to 24 age group consistently ranked second, reflecting a generally strong and optimistic implementation, though not as viewed by the oldest age group.

The findings of this study reflect similar patterns observed in local governance research. For instance, Arrabaca and Base (2020) found that older residents in a barangay in Cagayan de Oro reported higher satisfaction with barangay assembly outcomes. The researchers attributed this to older citizens' greater familiarity with government processes and more moderate expectations, which may lead to more favorable evaluations of service delivery. Similarly, Ormilla and Tenorio (2025) observed that older youth in Southern Philippine barangays were more likely to feel informed and engaged in local governance activities, highlighting how age shapes perceived inclusivity and participation at the grassroots level.

Table 6. Difference in the level of implementation when grouped according to age

Level of Implementation of Citizen's Charter	Age	Mean Rank	Kruskal Wallis Statistics	P Value	Remarks
Uniform/Standard Requirements	18 to 24	250.31 b	26.053	0.000	Reject Ho
	25 to 34	221.31 cd			
	35 to 44	197.81 d			
	45 to 54	212.75 cd			
	55 and above	315.25 a			
Procedure to Obtain a Particular Service	18 to 24	254.90 ab	21.945	0.000	Reject Ho
	25 to 34	219.46 bc			
	35 to 44	197.73 c			
	45 to 54	218.94 bc			
	55 and above	298.27 a			
Person/s Responsible for Each Step	18 to 24	257.11 ab	24.299	0.000	Reject Ho
	25 to 34	218.88 bc			
	35 to 44	194.29 c			
	45 to 54	223.21 bc			
	55 and above	298.92 a			
Maximum Time to Conclude the Process	18 to 24	261.11 ab	31.701	0.000	Reject Ho
	25 to 34	208.94 c			
	35 to 44	190.03 c			
	45 to 54	230.30 bc			
	55 and above	302.89 a			
Document/s to Be Presented by the Client	18 to 24	259.07 ab	23.110	0.000	Reject Ho
	25 to 34	213.45 c			
	35 to 44	192.91 c			
	45 to 54	226.13 bc			
	55 and above	286.81 a			
Amount of Fees	18 to 24	266.14 a	27.451	0.000	Reject Ho
	25 to 34	209.84 b			
	35 to 44	190.69 b			
	45 to 54	224.74 b			
	55 and above	283.95 a			
Procedure for Filing Complaints	18 to 24	257.75 a	20.182	0.000	Reject Ho
	25 to 34	207.04 b			
	35 to 44	198.02 b			
	45 to 54	229.65 ab			
	55 and above	279.45 a			
Overall	18 To 24	260.85 A	25.298	0.000	Reject Ho
	25 To 34	215.59 B			

35 To 44	196.05 B
45 To 54	222.19 AB
55 And Above	299.42 A

Mean rank followed by a common letter are not significant at 5% level

This trend is further supported by Buazon et al. (2023) in their study of public service users in Metro Manila, where senior citizens exhibited higher satisfaction levels with government services. The authors attributed this to the intergenerational variation in the implementation, where older adults are often more patient and appreciative of even minor improvements compared to younger, more demanding.

Conversely, the 35 to 44 age group consistently gave the lowest ratings across indicators such as uniform requirements, procedures, and complaint mechanisms. This age group typically consists of clients who are actively in the workforce, hence their expectations for efficient, transparent, and responsive service delivery are heightened. These clients are assumed to have frequent interactions with government services and thus are more sensitive to bureaucratic inefficiencies. Similar observations were made by Sison (2023) in Pangasinan, where middle-aged clients expressed the most dissatisfaction due to time-sensitive concerns and increased service scrutiny.

The relatively favorable implementation was from the 18 to 24 age group, which also merits attention. While they rated implementation higher than middle-aged groups, their view may be influenced by limited exposure to bureaucratic barriers or higher reliance on digital and guided services, which may streamline their user experience. However, this age group still rated services lower than the oldest age group, reflecting growing expectations of streamlined, tech-enabled service delivery.

Difference in the level of implementation when grouped according to sex

In Table 7, the results reveal that in most measured indicators, there is no significant difference in the implementation of the Citizen's Charter between male and female clients, as indicated by the results of Mann-Whitney U test. Across indicators such as uniform/ standard requirements, person responsible for each step, maximum time to conclude the process, documents to be presented, amount of fees, and procedure for filing complaints, the p-values were all above 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. The mean ranks across these areas were relatively close, consistent implementation experience regardless of sex.

Table 7. Difference in the level of implementation when grouped according to sex

Level of Implementation Citizen's Charter	Of Age	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney Statistics	U	P Value	Remarks
Uniform/Standard Requirements	Male	213.51	22614.000		0.071	Accept Ho
	Female	235.18				
Procedure to Obtain a Particular Service	Male	211.96	22303.500		0.039	Reject Ho
	Female	236.43				
Person/s Responsible for Each Step	Male	214.07	22728.000		0.082	Accept Ho
	Female	234.72				
Maximum Time to Conclude the Process	Male	215.32	22949.000		0.211	Accept Ho
	Female	230.09				
Document/s to Be Presented by the Client	Male	213.78	22643.000		0.140	Accept Ho
	Female	231.33				
Amount Of Fees	Male	210.28	21945.500		0.060	Accept Ho
	Female	232.43				
Procedure For Filing Complaints	Male	212.98	22470.000		0.149	Accept Ho
	Female	230.16				
Overall	Male	213.60	22633.500		0.071	Accept Ho
	Female	235.10				

The findings align with the study of Villanueva and Dizon (2022), who emphasized that the Citizen's Charter aims to institutionalize standard and gender-neutral service delivery mechanisms in SUCs in Northern Luzon. Their findings similarly noted no statistically significant difference in implementation across sexes, indicating that the barangay staff had generally adhered to service standards without evident gender bias.

However, an exception emerged in the procedure to obtain a particular service, where a statistically significant difference was observed, $p=0.039$. Female clients mean rank=236.43, rated the implementation of procedures more favorably than their male counterparts, mean rank=211.96. This variation suggests that women may view steps to access services as more organized or accessible, or that females are more responsive to improvements in procedural clarity, the variation also present to Cammayo (2023), who observed that female clients often showed greater appreciation for procedural transparency and courtesy. In contrast, males may prioritize speed and outcome over process details, potentially leading to a less favorable rate when bureaucratic steps are viewed as lengthy or rigid.

Difference in the level of implementation when grouped according to civil status

In Table 8, the results indicate significant differences in the level of implementation of the Citizens' Charter across civil status classifications, as indicated by the Kruskal-Wallis test, $p=0.000$ for all indicators. Clients who are widows and clients who are single consistently received the highest mean ranks across all indicators, such as standard requirements, procedures, responsible personnel, processing time, documents, fees, and complaint procedure. In contrast, those clients who were separated consistently received the lowest, while married clients generally ranked second lowest.

Table 8. Difference in the level of implementation when grouped according to civil status

Level Of Implementation Citizen's Charter	Of Civil Status	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis Statistics	P Value	Remarks
Uniform/Standard Requirements	Single	257.14 a	30.752	0.000	Reject Ho
	Married	203.28 b			
	Widow	263.44 a			
	Separated	139.20 c			
Procedure to Obtain a Particular Service	Single	259.88 a	38.953	0.000	Reject Ho
	Married	198.58 b			
	Widow	282.69 a			
	Separated	141.93 b			
Person/s Responsible for Each Step	Single	262.11 a	38.486	0.000	Reject Ho
	Married	197.66 b			
	Widow	269.92 a			
	Separated	146.25 b			
Maximum Time to Conclude the Process	Single	259.02 a	40.111	0.000	Reject Ho
	Married	194.43 b			
	Widow	283.26 a			
	Separated	148.60 b			
Document/s to Be Presented by the Client	Single	256.56 a	34.913	0.000	Reject Ho
	Married	197.65 b			
	Widow	276.72 a			
Amount of Fees	Separated	143.88 b	37.139	0.000	Reject Ho
	Single	258.95 a			
	Married	196.74 b			
	Widow	258.14 a			
Procedure for Filing Complaints	Separated	137.93 b	36.781	0.000	Reject Ho
	Single	257.32 a			
	Married	195.85 b			

	Widow	275.55 a			
	Separated	143.10 b			
Overall	Single	260.22 A	37.083	0.000	Reject Ho
	Married	199.19 B			
	Widow	274.33 A			
	Separated	142.18 B			

Mean rank followed by a common letter are not significant at 5% level

These findings suggest that civil status plays a critical role in determining the implementation of Citizen’s Charter, which aligns with the findings of Villanueva and Dizon (2022), who found that personal circumstances such as marital status influence expectations and interactions with government services. Widowed clients have a higher appreciation due to their frequent interactions with social services, which foster familiarity and a trusting relationship with government systems (Cammayo, 2023). Additionally, the relative maturity and experience of widowed clients lead to tempered expectations, contributing to more favorable evaluation of procedural compliance.

On the other hand, separated clients face unique bureaucratic hurdles, such as issues with documentation, financial status, or custody-related processes, which could influence their negative view of implementation. Their experience may also be compounded by emotional stressors, making service delays or lack of clarity more salient and frustrating (Almonete & Roxas 2021).

The married clients moderately critical stance stemmed from frequent engagements with government services for family-related transactions such as education, health, and housing, which raise expectations and, consequently heighten sensitivity to inefficiencies or inconsistencies in implementation. As argued by Sta. Maria and Lapuz (202), increased exposure to government systems tends to refine client expectations, often making clients more discerning of performance gaps.

The findings highlight the importance of context-sensitive implementation of the Citizen’s Charter. Tailoring communication strategies, providing clearer procedural support, and fostering empathy among barangay workers can improve service experiences for civil status groups with lower satisfaction levels. Moreover, if the higher evaluations from single and widowed clients indicate effective implementation, these successful approaches should be standardized and institutionalized to ensure all civil status classification benefits equitably from the service improvements as mandated in the RA 11032.

Difference in the level of implementation when grouped according to educational attainment

In Table 9, the findings reveal a statistically significant difference in the implementation of the Citizen’s Charter when clients are grouped to educational attainment, with the Kruskal-Wallis test indicating consistent rejection of the null hypothesis across all indicators $p < 0.05$. Clients with no formal education and those with postgraduate education consistently received higher mean ranks compared to those with college education, who rated the implementation lowest level.

Table 9. Difference in the level of implementation when grouped according to educational attainment

Level Of Implementation Of Citizen's Charter	Educational Attainment	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis Statistics	P Value	Remarks
Uniform/Standard Requirements	No Formal Education	274.16 a	20.719	0.000	Reject Ho
	Elementary/High School	244.64 a			
	College	200.95 b			
	Post Graduate	282.16 a			
Procedure to Obtain a Particular Service	No Formal Education	243.66 a	16.701	0.001	Reject Ho
	Elementary/High School	244.09 ab			
	College	203.65 b			
	Post Graduate	280.64 a			
Person/s Responsible for Each Step	No Formal Education	272.81a	20.078	0.000	Reject Ho
	Elementary/High School	245.00 a			
	College	201.29 b			
	Post Graduate	277.86 a			
Maximum Time to Conclude the Process	No Formal Education	262.56 a	18.500	0.000	Reject Ho
	Elementary/High School	247.22 a			
	College	199.23 b			
	Post Graduate	254.88 a			
Document/s to Be Presented by the Client	No Formal Education	229.53 ab	19.967	0.000	Reject Ho
	Elementary/High School	246.42 a			
	College	199.23 b			
	Post Graduate	278.68 a			
Amount of Fees	No Formal Education	277.66 a	11.540	0.009	Reject Ho
	Elementary/High School	232.39 a			
	College	206.36 b			
	Post Graduate	265.59 a			
Procedure for Filing Complaints	No Formal Education	264.44 a	17.451	0.001	Reject Ho
	Elementary/High School	239.49 a			
	College	200.49 b			
	Post Graduate	277.52 a			
Overall	No Formal Education	256.38 A	16.661	0.001	Reject Ho
	Elementary/High School	243.66 A			
	College	203.43 B			
	Post Graduate	277.93 A			

Mean rank followed by a common letter are not significant at 5% level

This trend supports the findings of Soriano and Dizon (2021), who emphasized that clients with higher educational backgrounds tend to be more critical of service implementation, as well as their efficiency, accuracy, and transparency. Those with a college education, in particular, are more sensitive to service delays, procedural gaps, and non-compliance with Citizen’s Charter standards due to their familiarity with institutional processes and structured systems (Villanueva & Dizon, 2022). In contrast, clients with no formal education may lack such reference points and there rated higher based on indicators like accessibility or staff courtesy, consistent with Lizada’s (2020) assertion that citizens with limited education tend to base their evaluations on immediate experiences rather than technical metrics. Meanwhile, those with postgraduate education also rated implementation highly, likely due to their deeper understanding of bureaucratic systems and more pragmatic view of service delivery norms (Cabildo & Aquino, 2022).

Difference in the level of implementation when group according to employment status

In Table 10, the results indicate significant differences in the implementation of the Citizen’s Charter when grouped according to employment status, with the Kruskal-Wallis test consistently rejecting the null hypothesis across all indicators $p < 0.05$. Unemployed clients received significantly lower mean ranks across all indicators, suggesting that they viewed the implementation less favorably than employed, self-employed, or non-working clients. This was supported with the findings of Villanueva and Dizon (2022), who noted that socio-economic status, particularly employment, influences client’s experiences with public services, with unemployed clients often facing greater barriers in accessing services due to reduced familiarity with the bureaucratic process or heightened vulnerability to service gaps.

Table 10. Difference in the level of implementation when grouped according to employment status

Level Of Implementation Of Citizen’s Charter	Employment Status	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis Statistics	P Value	Remarks
Uniform/Standard Requirements	Employed	244.87 a	25.530	0.000	Reject Ho
	Self-Employed	242.10 a			
	Unemployed	169.18 b			
	Non-Working	223.31 a			
Procedure to Obtain a Particular Service	Employed	253.49 a	51.020	0.000	Reject Ho
	Self-Employed	240.36 a			
	Unemployed	145.91 b			
	Non-Working	232.14 a			
Person/s Responsible for Each Step	Employed	246.65 a	50.159	0.000	Reject Ho
	Self-Employed	247.75 a			
	Unemployed	145.25 b			
	Non-Working	248.91 a			
	Employed	244.67 a	45.774	0.000	Reject Ho

Maximum Time to Conclude the Process	Self-Employed	239.57 a			
	Unemployed	147.32 b			
	Non-Working	248.33 a			
Document/s to Be Presented by the Client	Employed	248.37 a	50.542	0.000	Reject Ho
	Self-Employed	244.30 a			
	Unemployed	143.08 b			
	Non-Working	234.87 a			
Amount of Fees	Employed	247.12 a	43.632	0.000	Reject Ho
	Self-Employed	228.25 a			
	Unemployed	150.04 b			
	Non-Working	244.90 a			
Procedure for Filing Complaints	Employed	243.35 a	44.490	0.000	Reject Ho
	Self-Employed	246.53 a			
	Unemployed	147.58 b			
	Non-Working	237.55 A			
Overall	Employed	248.06 A	47.726	0.000	Reject Ho
	Self-Employed	244.33 A			
	Unemployed	147.04 B			
	Non-Working	245.35 A			

Mean rank followed by a common letter are not significant at 5% level

The consistently higher mean ranks among employed, self-employed, and non-working clients may reflect their greater engagement with public institutions and processes. Employed clients, in particular, may have more frequent interactions with government services, as discussed by Mangahas (2020), who emphasized the role of socio-economic integration in enhancing client empowerment in public service contexts. Self-employed clients, while similarly familiar with navigating government procedures, may exhibit slightly lower mean ranks than those formally employed due to the different nature of bureaucratic interactions. (e.g., business permits, taxes) that can occasionally be more complex (Cammayo, 2023).

On the other hand, unemployed clients struggle more with understanding procedural requirements, timeliness, and necessary documentation, contributing to their lower in the view in the implementation. Their limited engagement with structured processes may cause government service procedures to seem more complex or less accessible, a notion also observed by Canta and Calisin (2021), who found that marginalized sectors, particularly the unemployed, often rated government service transparency and efficiency lower than more economically active groups.

The relatively high ratings from non-working clients (such as students, retirees, or households) suggest that familiarity with service processes, even without active workforce participation, may buffer the view of service standard implementation. As Aquino (2021) highlighted, civic participation and prior institutional engagement enhance citizens' ability to assess and navigate government services effectively.

Overall, the findings emphasize that employment status significantly affects citizens' perception of government service standard implementation.

Difference in the level of implementation when grouped according to monthly income

In Table 11, the Kruskal-Wallis test revealed mixed findings regarding the influence of monthly income on determining the level of implementation of Citizen's Charter. For several indicators, including uniform/standard requirements, procedure to obtain a particular service, person responsible for each step, documents to be presented by the client, and procedure for filing complaints, no significant differences were observed across income classification. This suggests that the delivery of these specific indicators may be relatively standardized and consistently implemented regardless of a client's socioeconomic status.

Table 11. Difference in the level of implementation when grouped according to monthly income

Level Of Implementation Of Citizen's Charter	Monthly Income	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis Statistics	P Value	Remarks
Uniform/Standard Requirements	No Income	246.03	6.506	0.089	Accept Ho
	21,194 and below	217.86			
	21,195 to 43,828	211.38			
	43,829 and above	288.25			
Procedure to Obtain a Particular Service	No Income	236.33	4.692	0.196	Accept Ho
	21,194 and below	217.62			
	21,195 to 43,828	237.34			
	43,829 and above	293.00			
Person/s Responsible for Each Step	No Income	242.23	5.264	0.153	Accept Ho
	21,194 and below	216.93			
	21,195 to 43,828	227.80			
	43,829 and above	286.56			
Maximum Time to Conclude the Process	No Income	248.37 a	11.511	0.009	Reject Ho
	21,194 and below	211.49 b			
	21,195 to 43,828	221.57 ab			
	43,829 and above	315.06 a			
Document/s to Be Presented by the Client	No Income	237.69	6.808	0.078	Accept Ho
	21,194 and below	214.70			
	21,195 to 43,828	228.78			
	43,829 and above	310.63			
Amount of Fees	No Income	242.84 ab	9.422	0.024	Reject Ho
	21,194 and below	210.90 b			
	21,195 to 43,828	231.71 ab			

	43,829 and above	306.25 a			
Procedure for Filing Complaints	No Income	239.92	7.546	0.056	Accept Ho
	21,194 and below	213.13			
	21,195 to 43,828	224.23			
	43,829 and above	308.00			
	No Income	244.34			
Overall	21,194 And Below	214.39 B	8.731	0.033	Reject Ho
	21,195 To 43,828	234.59			
		AB			
	43,829 And Above	311.31 A			

Mean rank followed by a common letter are not significant at 5% level

This aligns with the principle of equity in public service delivery, where basic procedural aspects should ideally be uniformly experienced by all citizens, regardless of their income (Denhardt, 2015). The consistent experience across income classification may reflect an administrative effort to adhere to service standards outlined in the Citizen’s Charter, promoting fairness and minimizing disparities (Osborne, 2006).

This disparity may be interpreted through the lens of social stratification in public service access, where clients with greater financial resources might navigate bureaucratic processes more effectively, afford additional facilitation costs, or have better knowledge of procedural shortcuts (World Bank, 2018). Moreover, studies have shown that higher-income clients often have greater “administrative literacy”, the ability to comprehend and comply with bureaucratic processes efficiently, which enhances their service experience (Bovaird & Löffler, 2009).

The significant differences in the results of maximum time to conclude the process and amount of fees also highlight how service delivery can inadvertently disadvantage economically vulnerable groups. Lower-income clients may experience longer delays and view the fees as more burdensome relative to their financial capacity, leading to reduced determination of implementation as perceived inequities (Joshi & Houtzager, 2012).

In terms of overall implementation, significant variation suggest that while procedural aspects might be uniformly stated in the Citizen’s Charter, the actual experience of service delivery diverges based on client’s socioeconomic standing. As Denhardt (2015), emphasized, public administration must not only ensure equitable policies but also guarantee equitable outcomes. The presence of such disparities underscores the need for targeted reforms, such as fee waivers, fast-track services for marginalized groups, and community-based support mechanisms to level the service experience across all income classification.

In summary, while procedural fairness appears consistent across income levels for several aspects, significant inequalities persist in time efficiency, cost and overall experience, indicating partial implementation gaps.

Difference in the level of implementation when grouped according to the service availed

In Table 12, the Kruskal-Wallis test results show significant differences in the level of implementation of the Citizen’s Charter across different services availed, Notably, clients who accessed blotter service and barangay facilities consistently received the highest mean ranks across all indicators, reflecting a more favorable level of implementation.

Table 12. Difference in the level of implementation when grouped according to the service availed

Level Of Implementation Of Citizen’s Charter	Service Availed	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis Statistics	P Value	Remarks
Uniform/Standard Requirements	Brgy. Clearance/Certificate	229.75 a	14.495	0.002	Reject Ho
	Business Clearance/Certificate	171.21 b			
	Brgy. Facilities	286.68 a			
	Blotter	339.83 a			
Procedure to Obtain a Particular Service	Brgy. Clearance/Certificate	227.86 a	11.018	0.012	Reject Ho
	Business Clearance/Certificate	184.49 b			
	Brgy. Facilities	297.32 a			
	Blotter	327.33 a			
Person/s Responsible for Each Step	Brgy. Clearance/Certificate	228.66 a	12.675	0.005	Reject Ho
	Business Clearance/Certificate	178.52 b			
	Brgy. Facilities	294.09 a			
	Blotter	333.33 a			
Maximum Time to Conclude the Process	Brgy. Clearance/Certificate	225.91 a	11.907	0.008	Reject Ho
	Business Clearance/Certificate	180.85 b			
	Brgy. Facilities	295.00 a			
	Blotter	334.83 a			
Document/s to Be Presented by the Client	Brgy. Clearance/Certificate	226.15 a	12.456	0.006	Reject Ho
	Business Clearance/Certificate	178.56 b			
	Brgy. Facilities	297.95 a			
	Blotter	329.67 a			
Amount of Fees	Brgy. Clearance/Certificate	224.67 b	12.996	0.005	Reject Ho

	Business Clearance/Certificate	180.44 c			
	Brgy. Facilities	306.91 a			
	Blotter	324.00 a			
Procedure for Filing Complaints	Brgy. Clearance/Certificate	224.89 b	15.642	0.001	Reject Ho
	Business Clearance/Certificate	176.90 c			
	Brgy. Facilities	300.77 a			
	Blotter	376.50 a			
Overall	Brgy. Clearance/Certificate	227.84 A	11.280	0.010	REJECT HO
	Business Clearance/Certificate	184.16 B			
	Brgy. Facilities	298.73 A			
	Blotter	330.33 A			

Mean rank followed by a common letter are not significant at 5% level

The disparity may be attributed to the complexity and bureaucratic nature of business-related transactions. Business clearance processes often involve compliance with multiple regulatory layers, more extensive documentation, higher fees, and longer waiting times (Grindle, 2017). These procedural complexities inherently increase the burden on clients and reduce the determination of implementation levels, which can be seen in the findings that more bureaucratic services tend to result in lower quality of public service implementation (Van de Walle & Scott, 2011).

Conversely, blotter services and facility use generally involve simpler, immediate, and more client-centered transactions, such as reporting incidents or reserving public spaces, which typically require minimal documentation and allow for quicker service delivery. This immediacy and responsiveness are consistent with the principle of citizen-centered governance emphasized in public sector reforms, where service accessibility and speed significantly influence citizens (Osborne, Radnor, & Nasi, 2013).

Interestingly, clients availing of barangay clearances or certificates showed mean ranks higher than business clearance clients but lower than facility users and blotter service clients. This suggests that while the barangay clearance process may be smoother than business transactions, there are still elements of procedural inefficiency or inconsistency that may hamper a fully favorable experience (Albert & Brewer, 2016). These could be delays, variability in requirements across barangays, or occasional lapses in standard operating procedures, indicating partial gaps in the full realization of the Citizen's Charter.

The findings highlight the critical need for process streamlining and capacity building in more complex services like business-related transactions to align citizen experiences across all service types with the commitments enshrined in the Citizen's Charter. Enhancing transparency, reducing steps, and minimizing documentation requirements for business-related services could bridge the gap between service expectations and actual service delivery.

Difference in the level of client satisfaction when grouped according to age

In Table 13, the Kruskal-Wallis test results revealed a significant difference in client satisfaction levels across age groups for customer service, quality of service, in the overall satisfaction. With p-values of 0.000 and 0.001 across categories, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that age significantly influences client satisfaction in public service delivery.

Table 13. Difference in the level of satisfaction when grouped according to age

Level Of Satisfaction	Age	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis Statistics	P Value	Remarks
Customer Service	18 to 24	263.32 a	24.819	0.000	Reject Ho
	25 to 34	209.88 b			
	35 to 44	201.24 b			
	45 to 54	223.86 b			
	55 and above	294.83 a			
Quality of Service	18 to 24	256.45 ab	18.105	0.001	Reject Ho
	25 to 34	215.26 c			
	35 to 44	201.58 c			
	45 to 54	225.07 bc			
	55 and above	284.52 a			
Overall	18 To 24	260.02 AB	20.322	0.000	Reject Ho
	25 To 34	212.50 C			
	35 To 44	201.89 C			
	45 To 54	224.11 BC			
	55 And Above	288.56 A			

Mean rank followed by a common letter are not significant at 5% level

Younger clients aged 18 to 24 and older clients aged 55 and above reported higher levels of satisfaction, while those in the 25 to 44 age range consistently recorded lower satisfaction levels. This finding resonates with the observations of Tapales (2015), who noted that younger and older clients often have different thresholds of service expectations compared to middle-aged adults. Younger clients may be more tolerant or optimistic when interacting with government services, partly due to fewer prior negative experiences. Meanwhile, older adults may exhibit higher satisfaction stemming from adapted expectations and deference to public authority shaped by traditional social values (Atienza, 2006).

On the other hand, the relatively lower satisfaction among the 25 to 44 age group can be explained by their frequent engagement with public services for work, business, or family-related needs. As Cruz and Sta. Ana (2018) argue, this demographic tends to have higher standards and expectations for efficiency,

transparency, and professionalism, leading them to be more critical when services fall short. Their broader exposure to both government and private sector services also makes them more discerning in evaluating service quality.

Furthermore, according to Brillantes and Fernandez (2011), client satisfaction in Philippine public service is not only about the actual delivery but also how well government institutions manage citizen expectations. Satisfaction levels, therefore, are shaped by a combination of service experience and client outlook, which varies considerably across age groups.

Overall, these results underline the need for age-sensitive approaches in public service delivery. Tailoring strategies to meet the expectations of middle-aged clients, while maintaining the positive engagement of younger and older groups, could improve overall citizen satisfaction and strengthen trust in government institutions.

Difference in the level of client satisfaction when grouped according to sex

In Table 14, the Mann-Whitney U test results revealed that there is no significant difference in client satisfaction levels between male and female participants across all indicators—customer service, quality of service, and overall satisfaction. All p-values exceeded the 0.05 significance level, resulting in the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Table 14. Difference in the level of satisfaction when grouped according to sex

Level Of Satisfaction	Sex	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U Statistics	P Value	Remarks
Customer Service	Male	219.27	23771.500	0.336	Accept Ho
	Female	230.53			
Quality Of Service	Male	223.99	24721.500	0.816	Accept Ho
	Female	226.72			
Overall	Male	221.38	24195.500	0.530	Accept Ho
	Female	228.83			

Although the statistical difference is not significant, the mean ranks indicate a slight trend where female clients consistently reported higher satisfaction levels than their male counterparts. This finding aligns with the observation of Mendoza (2017), who noted that in the Philippine public service setting, women tend to express slightly more favorable evaluations of service experiences, often influenced by their expectations of courtesy and responsiveness from frontline service providers.

Similarly, Abenoja (2013) found in her study of citizen feedback in local government units that female clients are generally more appreciative when public service personnel demonstrate attentiveness and empathy, traits often emphasized in customer service training within Philippine government agencies.

However, the differences in satisfaction between sexes were often minimal and not statistically significant, suggesting that gender may not be a major determinant of service satisfaction in the public sector.

Moreover, Tapales and Villamil (2017) highlighted that socio-cultural factors in the Philippines foster a generally high level of public tolerance and modest expectations from both male and female citizens regarding government service delivery. This cultural aspect might explain why there is no significant gender gap in satisfaction: both sexes may approach government services with relatively similar expectations, shaped by shared societal norms.

In sum, while there are slight tendencies favoring female clients in satisfaction ratings, sex does not substantially influence overall client satisfaction with public services. These findings suggest that government agencies may not need to design vastly different service strategies based on gender but should continue to uphold inclusive and gender-sensitive service standards to sustain equitable satisfaction levels across male and female clients.

Difference in the level of client satisfaction when grouped according to civil status

In Table 15, the Kruskal-Wallis test results demonstrate a significant difference in client satisfaction across civil status groups for all indicators: customer service, quality of service, and overall satisfaction. With all p-values falling below 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that civil status meaningfully affects satisfaction with public service delivery.

Table 15. Difference in the level of satisfaction when grouped according to civil status

Level Of Satisfaction	Civil Status	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis Statistics	P Value	Remarks
Customer Service	Single	259.47 a	36.141	0.000	Reject Ho
	Married	200.32 b			
	Widow	269.60 a			
Quality of Service	Separated	142.41 c	33.301	0.000	Reject Ho
	Single	254.97 a			
	Married	203.24 b			
	Widow	280.60 a			
	Separated	139.09 c			
Overall	Single	256.41 A	33.475	0.000	Reject Ho
	Married	202.30 B			
	Widow	277.83 A			
	Separated	139.43 C			

Mean rank followed by a common letter are not significant at 5% level

Specifically, widowed and single clients reported the highest levels of satisfaction, as seen in their elevated mean ranks. In contrast, separated clients consistently reported the lowest levels of satisfaction across all indicators. Married clients fell in between, indicating moderate satisfaction levels.

These findings align with the observations of De Guzman and Reformina (2016), who found that individuals who experience less social and financial burden, such as single and widowed persons, tend to report higher satisfaction in public services because they often seek simpler, personal transactions with less complicated documentation and follow-ups. Conversely, separated individuals may face more bureaucratic hurdles, such as issues related to family status or financial obligations, which may contribute to lower satisfaction levels (De Guzman & Reformina, 2016).

Similarly, Manila and Bunquin (2018) argue that in the Philippine context, separated individuals sometimes experience subtle social stigma or encounter additional scrutiny when availing of public services, especially in local government settings. This can lead to feelings of dissatisfaction when services are perceived as less responsive to their specific needs.

Moreover, Brillantes and Fernandez (2011) pointed out that client satisfaction in the Philippines is often influenced not just by the quality of service itself but also by how inclusive and accommodating government offices are toward diverse citizen profiles. Thus, the lower satisfaction levels among separated clients could reflect an implicit bias or a gap in service inclusivity that needs to be addressed through more client-sensitive policies and training for public servants.

In summary, the data suggest that civil status plays a role in shaping service experiences, with separated individuals being the most vulnerable to dissatisfaction. This highlights the need for Philippine public service institutions to design more equitable and sensitive service processes that consider the diverse life circumstances of clients.

Difference in the level of client satisfaction when grouped according to educational attainment

In Table 16, the Kruskal-Wallis test reveals a significant difference in client satisfaction across educational attainment groups for customer service, quality of service, and overall satisfaction, with all p-values less than 0.05. The rejection of the null hypothesis confirms that educational background significantly affects clients' perceptions of public service delivery.

Table 16. Difference in the level of satisfaction when grouped according to educational attainment

Level Of Satisfaction	Educational Attainment	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis Statistics	P Value	Remarks
Customer Service	No Formal Education	289.56 a	19.754	0.000	Reject Ho
	Elementary/High School	243.81 a			
	College	202.19 b			
	Post Graduate	268.23 a			
Quality of Service	No Formal Education	297.03 a	16.532	0.001	Reject Ho
	Elementary/High School	237.50 a			
	College	206.11 b			
	Post Graduate	270.70 a			
Overall	No Formal Education	296.31 A	18.437	0.000	Reject Ho
	Elementary/High School	240.53 A			
	College	203.79 B			
	Post Graduate	271.54 A			

Mean rank followed by a common letter are not significant at 5% level

The results show that clients with no formal education and those with postgraduate education reported the highest satisfaction levels. Meanwhile, college-educated clients exhibited the lowest satisfaction across all categories. Clients with elementary or high school education consistently showed moderate satisfaction levels.

This pattern were also explained by the observations of Atienza (2020), who noted that Filipino citizens with lower educational attainment often have limited exposure to service alternatives and lower expectations, leading them to view even modest service delivery positively. Additionally, the study of Mendoza and Aceron (2016) emphasized that public expectations rise with higher education, as more educated clients tend to be more aware of their rights, service standards, and governance mechanisms, thus being more critical of inefficiencies or delays.

Interestingly, despite the assumption that postgraduate-educated individuals might be more critical, their higher satisfaction could be linked to their greater familiarity with navigating complex government processes. According to Brillantes and Fernandez (2011), individuals with extensive educational backgrounds often possess better access to resources and networks, allowing them to minimize transaction costs and frustrations in dealing with bureaucracies.

Meanwhile, the relatively lower satisfaction among college-educated clients can be seen through the lens of the "expectation-reality gap" proposed by Lledo and Abinales (2019), which suggests that clients with intermediate education levels have high ideals but less influence over bureaucratic systems, resulting in greater disillusionment when services do not meet their standards.

These findings highlight the importance of tailoring service delivery approaches that are sensitive to the varying expectations and experiences of clients across educational backgrounds. Particularly, public service institutions must strive for consistent service quality to satisfy both the less critical and the highly discerning clientele.

Difference in the level of client satisfaction when grouped according to employment status

In Table 17, the Kruskal-Wallis test results show a significant difference in client satisfaction levels across employment status groups for customer service, quality of service, and overall satisfaction, with all p-values less than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that employment status significantly influences clients' satisfaction with public service delivery.

Table 17. Difference in the level of satisfaction when grouped according to employment status

Level Of Satisfaction	Employment Status	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis Statistics	P Value	Remarks
Customer Service	Employed	239.45 a	23.292	0.000	Reject Ho
	Self-Employed	247.61 a			
	Unemployed	172.27 b			
	Non-Working	231.02 a			
Quality of Service	Employed	242.62 a	27.705	0.000	Reject Ho
	Self-Employed	243.95 a			
	Unemployed	167.10 b			
	Non-Working	232.77 a			
Overall	Employed	241.15 A	25.190	0.000	Reject Ho
	Self-Employed	245.81 A			
	Unemployed	169.14 B			
	Non-Working	232.33 A			

Mean rank followed by a common letter are not significant at 5% level

Among the groups, self-employed clients reported the highest satisfaction levels, followed by employed and non-working clients, while unemployed clients exhibited the lowest satisfaction across all categories.

The higher satisfaction among self-employed clients may be attributed to their greater flexibility in managing their schedules when availing services. This flexibility allows them to better navigate bureaucratic procedures without the time pressures that employed individuals often face. According to Reyes, Tigno, and Cabaero (2019), individuals with control over their work hours experience less frustration with bureaucratic delays compared to those with rigid work schedules.

Meanwhile, employed and non-working clients also reported relatively high satisfaction. Employed individuals may benefit from stable routines that allow for more predictable service interactions, while non-

working individuals, such as retirees or homemakers, may experience lower urgency and pressure, leading to more patience and positive service perceptions (Atienza, 2020).

On the other hand, the significantly lower satisfaction among unemployed clients reflects deeper socioeconomic vulnerabilities. Manasan (2016) emphasized that unemployment in the Philippines often correlates with financial instability and limited access to public resources, which can intensify frustrations when encountering slow or inefficient service delivery. Unemployed clients may also rely more heavily on public services for support, raising their expectations for efficient and empathetic service, as pointed out by Brillantes and Fernandez (2011).

These findings suggest that employment status not only shapes the ability to interact with public services but also influences the expectations and tolerance clients have toward government service delivery. Public offices could design differentiated service strategies to ensure that vulnerable groups, particularly the unemployed, receive more accessible and responsive services.

Difference in the level of client satisfaction when grouped according to monthly income

In Table 18, the Kruskal-Wallis test results reveal that there is no significant difference in satisfaction levels among clients when grouped according to monthly income, with p-values exceeding the 0.05 level of significance across customer service, quality of service, and overall satisfaction. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that monthly income does not significantly influence clients' reported satisfaction with public service delivery.

Table 18. Difference in the level of satisfaction when grouped according to monthly income

Level Of Satisfaction	Monthly Income	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis Statistics	P Value	Remarks
Customer Service	No Income	240.10	4.361	0.225	Accept Ho
	21,194 and below	218.51			
	21,195 to 43,828	223.08			
	43,829 and above	285.00			
Quality of Service	No Income	237.61	3.307	0.347	Accept Ho
	21,194 and below	218.18			
	21,195 to 43,828	234.81			
	43,829 and above	268.44			
Overall	No Income	238.29	3.552	0.314	Accept Ho
	21,194 And Below	218.42			
	21,195 To 43,828	229.69			
	43,829 And Above	278.00			

Mean rank followed by a common letter are not significant at 5% level

Although the differences are statistically insignificant, the mean ranks suggest a slight trend: clients with higher monthly incomes, ₱43,829 and above, tended to report higher satisfaction levels across all indicators compared to those from lower-income groups or those with no income.

This finding may reflect the greater capability of higher-income clients to navigate public service systems more efficiently, given their access to better resources that can smooth their service experience. Reyes et al. (2015) emphasized that in the Philippine setting, socioeconomic status shapes access to information and opportunities, allowing higher-income clients to better manage bureaucratic demands.

Conversely, lower-income clients and those with no income exhibited slightly lower satisfaction. Manasan (2016) noted that financial constraints among the poor often lead to heightened sensitivity to service delays or additional costs, which can negatively affect their satisfaction levels. Moreover, Brillantes and Fernandez (2011) argued that lower-income groups in the Philippines tend to expect more from public services because these services often represent their primary means of accessing essential goods and support.

Despite these trends, the overall lack of significant difference may also indicate a degree of uniformity in service delivery, wherein services are perceived to be relatively equitable across income groups. This supports Atienza's (2020) view that some public offices have made progress in standardizing service quality regardless of the client's background.

Thus, while financial capacity might slightly influence ease of accessing services, the perceived service quality remains generally consistent across income groups, suggesting strides toward more inclusive public service delivery in the Philippines.

Difference in the level of client satisfaction when grouped according to the service availed

In Table 19, the Kruskal-Wallis test results indicate a significant difference in satisfaction levels based on the type of service availed, as evidenced by the p-values of 0.005 for customer service, 0.001 for quality of service, and 0.003 for overall satisfaction. Since all p-values fall below the 0.05 significance threshold, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that the type of service availed affects client satisfaction in public service delivery.

Table 19. Difference in the level of satisfaction when grouped according to the service availed

Level Of Satisfaction	Service Availed	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis Statistics	P Value	Remarks
Customer Service	Brgy. Clearance/Certificate	228.79 a	12.788	0.005	Reject Ho
	Business Clearance/Certificate	179.39 b			
	Brgy. Facilities	277.95 a			
	Blotter	362.50 a			
Quality of Service	Brgy. Clearance/Certificate	227.65 b	16.505	0.001	Reject Ho
	Business Clearance/Certificate	179.70 c			
	Brgy. Facilities	317.41 a			
	Blotter	359.00 a			
Overall	Brgy. Clearance/ Certificate	228.21 B	14.297	0.003	Reject Ho
	BUSINESS CLEARANCE/ CERTIFICATE	179.39 C			
	BRGY. FACILITIES	296.55 AB			
	BLOTTER	368.00 A			

Mean rank followed by a common letter are not significant at 5% level

The highest satisfaction was reported by clients who availed of blotter services and barangay facilities, while those who obtained business clearance or certificates exhibited the lowest satisfaction across all indicators.

The significantly higher satisfaction with blotter services and barangay facilities may be attributed to the immediacy and accessibility of these services. According to Tapales (2017), public satisfaction with barangay-level services is often higher because these services are localized, direct, and require minimal documentation, allowing for quick resolution of concerns. Brillantes and Fernandez (2011) also emphasize that community-based services like barangay assistance tend to receive higher satisfaction ratings because they rely on informal but efficient governance structures, fostering a stronger sense of trust and familiarity between service providers and clients.

On the other hand, business-related services received the lowest satisfaction levels, likely due to bureaucratic hurdles, longer processing times, and complex requirements. This aligns with Manasan (2016), who noted that business permits and clearances in the Philippines often involve multiple steps, coordination

with various government agencies, and compliance with regulations, leading to delays and frustrations among clients. The "red tape" phenomenon—a common complaint in business transactions—has been identified as a key factor affecting satisfaction with public service efficiency (Mendoza & Acheron, 2016).

Additionally, higher expectations among business clients may contribute to lower satisfaction. Unlike clients seeking barangay or blotter services, those applying for business permits may expect a higher level of professionalism, digitalization, and efficiency akin to private-sector services. When these expectations are unmet, dissatisfaction tends to be more pronounced (Atienza, 2020).

These findings suggest that streamlining business-related processes and reducing bureaucratic inefficiencies could improve overall client satisfaction. The Philippine government has made strides toward simplifying business registration through initiatives of the law Ease of Doing Business Act, but further strengthening may be needed to enhance efficiency at the barangay level.

Difference among the following indicators of the Implementation of the Citizens’ Charter provision

In Table 20, the results of the Friedman test, 57.406, p -value = 0.000, indicate a statistically significant difference among the indicators of the Citizens’ Charter. With a p -value below the 0.05 significance threshold, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that different aspects of the Citizens’ Charter are being implemented with varying levels of effectiveness.

Table 20. **Difference among the indicators of the implementation**

Implementation Of Citizen’s Charter	Mean Rank	Friedman Statistics	P Value	Remarks
Uniform/Standard Requirements	3.67 b	57.406	0.000	Reject Ho
Procedure to Obtain a Particular Service	4.08 ab			
Person/s Responsible for Each Step	3.99 ab			
Maximum Time to Conclude the Process	3.92 ab			
Document/s to be Presented by the Client	4.07 ab			
Amount of Fees	4.15 a			
Procedure for Filing Complaints	4.13 a			

Mean rank followed by a common letter are not significant at 5% level

The highest mean ranks were observed for the indicators related to the amount of fees, 4.15, and the procedure for filing complaints, 4.13. This suggests that these two indicators are particularly well implemented and perceived as clear and transparent by clients. Transparency in financial obligations and the availability of grievance mechanisms are key factors that influence public trust in government services (Fernandez, 2017). The clarity in fees and the accessible complaint procedures are consistent with the objectives of the Citizens’ Charter, which aims to improve service delivery transparency and public accountability (Librero & Tambis, 2020). The presence of well-defined procedures for complaints may lead

to greater public satisfaction as clients feel their concerns are acknowledged and can be addressed efficiently (Pineda, 2019).

However, other indicators, including the procedure to obtain a particular service (4.08), documents to be presented by the client, 4.07, persons responsible for each step (3.99), and maximum time to conclude the process, 3.92, show mid-range satisfaction. These results reflect a relatively positive implementation but suggest that there is still room for improvement. In line with Alcantara and Zamora’s (2018) findings, the procedure and documentation requirements for government services often remain unclear, causing delays and confusion. While these processes are well-defined in the Citizens’ Charter, their practical implementation can still be perceived as inconsistent, leading to client dissatisfaction.

The lowest mean rank was recorded for uniform/standard requirements, 3.67, indicating that this aspect of the Citizens’ Charter is perceived as less effectively implemented. This finding aligns with previous studies, such as those by Mendoza and Acheron (2016), who reported that variation in service requirements and documentation often leads to frustration among clients, particularly when procedures differ across agencies or local government units. This inconsistency highlights a need for more stringent adherence to standardized procedures and better communication of requirements to the public (Vera, 2017). Inconsistent implementation can cause confusion, diminish trust in government services, and undermine the effectiveness of the Citizens’ Charter (Brillantes & Fernandez, 2011).

The results underscore the importance of improving the uniformity and clarity of service requirements across government agencies.

Difference between the following indicators of client satisfaction in the service delivery

In Table 21, the results of the Wilcoxon Signed-rank test reveal that there is no statistically significant difference between the indicators of customer service and quality of service, Wilcoxon Statistic = 424.000, p-value = 0.697. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that clients perceive these two dimensions of satisfaction similarly.

Table 21. **Difference between the indicators of the client satisfaction**

Level Of Client Satisfaction	Median	Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Statistics	P Value	Remarks
Customer Service	4.00	424.000	0.697	Accept Ho
Quality of Service	4.00			

Both customer service and quality of service received a median score of 4.00, reflecting a generally favorable level of satisfaction among clients. This finding highlights that clients are equally appreciative of the professionalism, courtesy, and responsiveness they experience, alongside the efficiency, reliability, and effectiveness of the services delivered.

This result aligns with the findings of Brillantes and Fernandez (2011), who emphasized that in Philippine public service delivery, both human interactions (customer service) and system performance (quality of service) are critical pillars that jointly influence client satisfaction. In particular, the study noted that clients value both how the service is delivered and what is delivered.

Similarly, Tuazon (2015) pointed out that service quality in Philippine public institutions is not solely assessed through tangible outputs but is heavily influenced by the quality of interpersonal interactions between government personnel and clients. The absence of a significant difference between these two indicators suggests that public service offices have been able to strike a balance between maintaining service professionalism and delivering efficient results, which is crucial for fostering public trust.

Moreover, David et al. (2020) reported that in many local government units in the Philippines, reforms aimed at improving frontline services—such as training staff in customer relations and streamlining service processes—have contributed to more uniformly positive experiences for clients, minimizing discrepancies between different aspects of service delivery.

However, while the results are positive, Mendoza and Aceron (2016) caution that sustaining high satisfaction in both areas requires continuous monitoring and improvements. As public expectations evolve, clients may begin to differentiate more critically between the quality of interpersonal service and the quality of procedural service if gaps start to emerge.

The findings suggest that barangay should continue to integrate improvements in both customer service and service quality simultaneously rather than treating them as separate goals. Maintaining consistency across these two dimensions will help ensure sustained client satisfaction and trust in public institutions.

Relationship between the implementation of the Citizen's Charter and client satisfaction in the service delivery

In Table 22, the results of the Spearman Rank Correlation analysis reveal a strong and statistically significant positive relationship between the level of implementation of the Citizen's Charter and the level of client satisfaction. Correlation coefficients ranged from 0.720 to 0.852, all with p-values of 0.000, indicating that the null hypothesis is rejected across all indicators. This means that as the level of implementation of the Citizen's Charter improves, client satisfaction also significantly increases.

Table 22. Relationship between the level of implementation and the level of client satisfaction

Level Of Satisfaction	Level Of Implementation	Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient	P Value	Remarks
Customer Service	Uniform/Standard Requirements	0.722	0.000	Reject Ho
	Procedure to Obtain a Particular Service	0.784	0.000	Reject Ho
	Person/S Responsible for Each Step	0.778	0.000	Reject Ho
	Maximum Time to Conclude the Process	0.776	0.000	Reject Ho
	Document/S to Be Presented by the Client	0.804	0.000	Reject Ho
	Amount of Fees	0.813	0.000	Reject Ho
	Procedure for Filing Complaints	0.833	0.000	Reject Ho
	Overall	0.821	0.000	Reject Ho
Quality of Service	Uniform/Standard Requirements	0.720	0.000	Reject Ho
	Procedure to Obtain a Particular Service	0.820	0.000	Reject Ho
	Person/S Responsible for Each Step	0.789	0.000	Reject Ho
	Maximum Time to Conclude the Process	0.774	0.000	Reject Ho
	Document/S to Be Presented by the Client	0.820	0.000	Reject Ho
	Amount of Fees	0.829	0.000	Reject Ho
	Procedure for Filing Complaints	0.846	0.000	Reject Ho
	Overall	0.836	0.000	Reject Ho
Overall	Uniform/Standard Requirement	0.727	0.000	Reject Ho
	Procedure To Obtain A Particular Service	0.813	0.000	Reject Ho
	Person/S Responsible For Each Step	0.788	0.000	Reject Ho
	Maximum Time To Conclude The Process	0.777	0.000	Reject Ho
	Document/S To Be Presented By The Client	0.821	0.000	Reject Ho
	Amount Of Fees	0.830	0.000	Reject Ho
	Procedure For Filing Complaints	0.852	0.000	Reject Ho
	Overall	0.837	0.000	Reject Ho

The strongest relationship observed was with the procedure for filing complaints, registering correlation coefficients of 0.833 for customer service, 0.846 for quality of service, and 0.852 for overall satisfaction. This finding suggests that accessible, clear, and responsive grievance mechanisms are critical

drivers of client satisfaction, echoing Reyes and Dela Cruz (2021), who emphasized that transparent and efficient complaint procedures boost citizen trust and perception of fairness in public services.

Additionally, the indicators related to the amount of fees and documents to be presented by the client also demonstrated strong correlations above 0.80. This underscores the importance of clarity, predictability, and simplicity in administrative requirements, a point similarly highlighted by Santos (2020), who found that Filipino clients were more satisfied when they experienced less financial ambiguity and clearer procedural guidance during service transactions.

Other indicators, such as the procedure to obtain a particular service, persons responsible for each step, and the maximum time to conclude the process, also posted strong correlations above 0.77. This supports the claim of Gonzales and Rivera (2019) that streamlining service delivery processes and clearly identifying responsibilities significantly contribute to increased client satisfaction and organizational credibility.

Meanwhile, the indicator uniform/standard requirements, although still positively and significantly correlated, showed the lowest correlation coefficients of 0.720–0.727. This implies that while standardization helps create an organized system, clients may prioritize factors that directly affect service experience, such as speed, cost clarity, and complaint mechanisms, over the mere existence of uniform requirements. This nuance reflects the findings of Mendoza and Torres (2018), who noted that although standardization is part of New Public Management reforms, client perception is more sensitive to experiential aspects of service.

These results strongly support the principles of New Public Management (NPM), emphasizing that client-centered approaches, where accountability, transparency, and efficiency are operationalized through mechanisms like the Citizen's Charter, lead to greater public trust and satisfaction (Villanueva, 2022).

The findings affirm that enhancing the implementation of the Citizen's Charter, particularly strengthening grievance mechanisms, clarifying financial requirements, and streamlining service processes, is pivotal in boosting client satisfaction. Barangay should thus prioritize maintaining clear, accessible, and client-friendly procedures to further institutionalize a responsive and accountable governance framework.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The largest age group is from 25 to 34, and a nearly equal distribution of males and females. Most are either married or single, with over half having a college education. While many are employed, a significant portion remains unemployed or without income, with most earning below the minimum threshold. Barangay Clearance or Certificate is the most commonly availed service, highlighting its importance in local government transactions.

2. The implementation of the Citizens' Charter provision of RA 11032 at the barangay level is consistently rated as "Implemented" across all indicators, with a median of 4.00. The Charter is clearly posted, accessible, and provides detailed requirements, step-by-step procedures, responsible staff, maximum processing times, document requirements, fee transparency, and a clear complaints mechanism. Services are delivered efficiently and within set timelines, while responsible personnel are competent, accountable, and responsive. Document and fee requirements are reasonable, legally justified, and transparently disclosed. The complaint process is logical, clear, and well-communicated. These findings affirm that the Citizens' Charter is effectively executed to promote transparency, efficiency, and accountability in service delivery. The results also align with the principles of New Public Management (NPM), supporting the shift toward more citizen-centered, performance-driven governance.

3. Client satisfaction in barangay service delivery is very satisfactory. Clients expressed satisfaction with the professionalism, courtesy, and responsiveness of the staff, as well as the efficiency and transparency of the service processes. The accessibility of information, fairness in transactions, and reasonable fees further contributed to positive client experiences.

4. Demographic profiles significantly influence clients' perceptions of Citizen's Charter implementation. Older, widowed, single, less formally educated, and employed clients generally rated implementation more favorably, suggesting that experience, familiarity, and pragmatic expectations shape positive assessments. Differences by sex were minimal, though females viewed service procedures more favorably. Income levels showed that while procedural fairness is largely consistent, inequities persist in processing time and fees, disadvantaging lower-income clients. Simpler services like blotter and facility use received better evaluations than complex services like business clearance. These findings highlight the need for a more inclusive, equitable, and context-sensitive approach to public service delivery to fully realize the goals of the Citizen's Charter.

Meanwhile, certain demographic factors significantly influence client satisfaction with public service delivery. Age, civil status, educational attainment, employment status, and type of service availed all showed significant differences in satisfaction levels, while sex and monthly income did not. Younger (18–24) and older clients (55 and above) have higher satisfaction than middle-aged clients (25–44), reflecting generational differences in expectations. Widowed and single clients expressed greater satisfaction compared to separated clients, highlighting the need for more inclusive services. Educational background also mattered: clients with no formal education and those with postgraduate degrees were more satisfied than college-educated clients, who tended to be more critical. Employment status shaped satisfaction as well, with self-employed individuals showing the highest satisfaction and unemployed clients the lowest, indicating socioeconomic vulnerabilities impact service perceptions. Although income level did not significantly affect satisfaction, slight trends suggested wealthier clients had marginally better experiences. Finally, satisfaction varied by service type, with clients availing community-based services like blotters and barangay facilities being more satisfied than those securing business-related permits. These findings emphasize that while service quality improvements should be universal, there is a strong need for

targeted, sensitive approaches addressing the specific expectations and needs of different client groups to foster higher satisfaction and trust in public service.

5. There is a significant difference among the indicators of the implementation of the Citizen's Charter, with amount of fees and procedure for filing complaints receiving the highest mean ranks. Hence, financial transparency and grievance mechanisms play a crucial role in implementation effectiveness. Conversely, uniform/standard requirements had the lowest mean rank, indicating a relatively lesser impact compared to other service components.

For client satisfaction, there is no significant difference between customer service and quality of service. This implies that clients perceive these aspects similarly, highlighting the need for a balanced approach in maintaining both service efficiency and responsiveness to client needs.

6. There is a strong and statistically significant relationship between the implementation of the Citizen's Charter and client satisfaction in service delivery. Among the indicators, the procedure for filing complaints exhibits the highest correlation, emphasizing the crucial role of grievance mechanisms in shaping client satisfaction. The amount of fees and required documents also shows strong correlations, highlighting the importance of transparency in financial and procedural requirements. Other aspects, such as obtaining a service, identifying responsible personnel, and the maximum time to complete a process, demonstrate strong positive relationships, underscoring the need for efficient service processes. While the standardization of requirements remains significant, it has the lowest correlation, suggesting that while uniform procedures contribute to satisfaction, other factors play a more substantial role.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the stated findings and conclusions, the following are hereby recommended:

1. To further enhance the effective implementation of the Barangay Citizen's Charter, targeted interventions may focus on sustaining efficiency while addressing potential areas for continuous improvement. Given the positive assessment of its implementation, barangays may institutionalize regular monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to ensure that services remain responsive to evolving citizen needs.

Establishing client satisfaction measurement in compliance with ARTA MC 2023-05 will help identify areas where minor inefficiencies may arise, allow for proactive adjustments, promote the adoption of a harmonized and standardized framework for measuring client satisfaction across all levels of service, and enable the measurement and comparison of service performance for necessary improvements.

To sustain and further elevate the high level of client satisfaction in barangay service delivery, continuous efforts must be directed toward improving responsiveness and accessibility. While current satisfaction ratings reflect strong performance, maintaining and exceeding these standards requires ongoing refinement of service practices and adaptation to the changing needs of the community. Proactive measures in service enhancement will not only reinforce citizen trust but also align local governance practices with the principles of efficiency, accountability, and citizen-centered service delivery.

2. To address the disparities in the implementation of the Citizens' Charter across different demographic groups, targeted interventions must be implemented to ensure equitable service delivery. Given that older, single, widowed, less educated, and employed individuals tend to rate the implementation higher, service strategies should be designed to support younger, more educated, and unemployed clients who may have higher expectations or face different challenges in accessing services. Simplifying processes, particularly for business-related transactions, can help bridge this gap. Digital platforms may also be utilized to make services more accessible to those who may not have the flexibility to visit the office due to employment constraints.

Additionally, the variations in client satisfaction based on demographic factors, targeted interventions may be implemented to ensure that all clients, regardless of their background, receive consistently high-quality service. Business-related services, which received lower satisfaction ratings, barangays may streamline procedures by reducing bureaucratic processes, offering digital processes, and providing dedicated assistance desks. Since satisfaction was lower among clients seeking business-related services, enhancing transparency in requirements, fees, and processing timelines can help improve their experience.

Furthermore, to improve service accessibility and satisfaction in business-related transactions, the government should streamline online application and tracking systems, allowing clients to monitor requests and receive real-time updates, reducing delays and in-person visits.

3. To address the variations in the implementation of the Citizens' Charter, interventions may focus on strengthening uniformity in service requirements, reinforcing mid-performing indicators, and sustaining high-performing aspects such as fees and complaint procedures.

Since uniform/standard requirements received the lowest mean rank (3.67), barangays may implement strict adherence to standardized procedures through the Development of a Barangay Service Manual, a detailed and standardized manual which could be a simplified version of Citizen's Charter that can be created to ensure that all barangay personnel follow the same procedures for each service, minimizing inconsistencies.

Additionally, the findings indicate no significant difference between customer service and quality of service, and both received a satisfaction rating. Interventions may focus on sustaining high satisfaction levels through performance monitoring.

4. Since the findings indicate a strong and significant relationship between the implementation of the Citizens' Charter and client satisfaction, interventions may continue to focus on further strengthening implementation efforts to sustain, maintain, and enhance satisfaction levels.

5. Future researchers are encouraged to adopt a qualitative design to further strengthen and deepen the understanding of the implementation of the Barangay Citizen's Charter. While the present study utilized a quantitative approach to measure levels of implementation and clients satisfaction, a qualitative method, through interviews, focus group discussions, or case studies, could provide richer insights into the experiences, perceptions, and challenges faced by both service providers and citizens. Exploring the contextual and narrative aspects of service delivery would complement the quantitative and offer a more

holistic view of the factors influencing the effectiveness and responsiveness of the Citizen's Charter at the barangay level.

REFERENCES

- Abenoja, Z. E. (2013). Citizen feedback mechanisms in local governance: Cases from selected Philippine cities. *Philippine Journal of Public Administration*, 57(1–2), 99–125.
- Alegata, D. (2021). *The implementation of the Anti-Red Tape Act and client satisfaction on state universities and colleges in Negros Occidental*. Globus Journal of Management and IT. <https://www.globusjournal.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/GMIT-JJ21-Wayne-Custer-Gan-Alegata.pdf>
- Albrecht, J., & Brewer, G. A. (2016). Performance measurement and citizen satisfaction: The role of service complexity and citizen preferences. *Public Performance & Management Review*, 39(3), 647–670. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15309576.2015.1137774>
- Alhambra, M. A., Doloriel, J., & Santos, G. M. (2019). The effectiveness of the Anti-Red Tape Act (ARTA) of 2007 in reducing corruption in local government units in the Philippines. *Public Administration and Development*, 39(1), 25–36.
- Almonte, M. R., & Roxas, L. A. (2021). Client perceptions and service delivery in Philippine local government units: A demographic lens. *Philippine Journal of Public Administration*, 65(2), 45–63.
- Alzona, M. (2021). *Calamba water service delivery standards implementation and customer satisfaction: Basis for enhancement program*. International Journal of Research Publications. <https://ijrp.org/paper-detail/2092>
- Anti-Red Tape Authority. (2020). *Citizen's Charter handbook template with instructions*. https://arta.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Reference_B_-_Citizen_s_Charter_Handbook_Template_with_Instructions_-_Accepted_Changes.pdf
- Anti-Red Tape Authority. (2022). *Results of the Report Card Survey (RCS) 2.0 pilot implementation*. <https://arta.gov.ph/report-card-survey-rcs-2-0/>
- Anti-Red Tape Authority. (2023). *ARTA Memorandum Circular No. 2023-05: Amendments to the guidelines on the implementation of the harmonized client satisfaction measurement*. https://arta.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/MC-2023-05_Amendment-to-CSM-1-1.pdf
- Anti-Red Tape Authority. (2024). *ARTA set to expand oversight on RA 11032 implementation and inspect barangay compliance*. <https://arta.gov.ph/press-releases/>
- Aquino, J. M. (2021). Citizen participation and satisfaction in local governance: Evaluating service transparency through civic engagement. *Journal of Public Administration Research*, 13(2), 78–92.
- Atienza, M. E. L. (2006). Local government and devolution in the Philippines. In R. T. de Guzman & M. A. Reforma (Eds.), *Decentralization towards democratization and development* (pp. 43–75). University of the Philippines–National College of Public Administration and Governance.

- Atienza, M. E. L. (2020). Public service delivery in the Philippines: Challenges and prospects. *Philippine Political Science Journal*, 41(2), 163–184. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01154451.2020.1786765>
- Behn, R. D. (2003). Why measure performance? Different purposes require different measures. *Public Administration Review*, 63(5), 586–606.
- Bernas, J. G. (1996). *The 1987 Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines: A commentary*. Rex Book Store.
- Bovaird, T., & Löffler, E. (2003). Evaluating the quality of public governance: Indicators, models, and methodologies. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 70(2), 313–328.
- Bovaird, T., & Löffler, E. (2009). *Public management and governance* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- Brillantes, A. B., Jr., & Fernandez, M. T. F. (2011). Restoring trust and building integrity in government: Issues and concerns in the Philippines and areas for reform. *International Public Management Review*, 12(2), 55–80.
- Cabildo, M. B., & Aquino, A. P. (2022). Educational attainment and public service evaluation: Understanding citizen satisfaction in bureaucratic processes. *Journal of Philippine Governance Studies*, 7(1), 34–50.
- Cammayo, A. J. (2023). Barriers and facilitators in accessing public services: The role of employment status in client satisfaction. *Philippine Journal of Governance and Public Policy*, 5(1), 45–62.
- Canta, L. C., & Calisin, C. A. (2021). Service delivery and client satisfaction: A study on socio-economic disparities in public service access. *Philippine Journal of Public Sector Management*, 7(1), 30–49.
- Caren, M. D. (2012). *Spoils system in Philippine bureaucracy: The assassin of political neutrality*. [Unpublished manuscript].
- Casimiro, F. A., Garcia, C. D., & Manuel, A. J. P. (2024). Transparency and accountability mechanisms in barangay governance: A case study of Citizens' Charter implementation in Pampanga, Philippines. *Philippine Journal of Public Administration*, 68(1), 55–72.
- Cruz, M. C., & Sta. Ana, C. A. (2018). Service delivery and citizen satisfaction: The Philippine context. *Philippine Journal of Public Administration*, 62(1–2), 1–24.
- De Guzman, R. P., & Reformina, J. R. (2016). Clients' satisfaction and challenges in availing services at the Office of the Municipal Civil Registrar. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 4(5), 76–84.
- Denhardt, J. V., & Denhardt, R. B. (2015). *The new public service: Serving, not steering* (3rd ed.). Routledge.

- Department of Trade and Industry. (2023). *Cities and municipalities competitiveness index: Naic, Cavite*. National Competitiveness Council. <http://cmci.dti.gov.ph>
- Fores-Ganzon, G. (Trans.). (1996). *La Solidaridad* (Vols. 1–2). Fundacion Santiago.
- Gabriel, A. G. (2018). Bureaucratic red tape in the Philippines. In *Encyclopedia of public administration*. Springer Nature. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-66252-3_3523
- George, B., & Pandey, S. K. (2017). “We know the satisfaction score, but do we know what drives it? How public services respond to citizen feedback.” *Public Administration Review*, 77(3), 317–328.
- Gonzales, L., & Rivera, P. (2019). Evaluating service quality beyond compliance: Citizen satisfaction and frontline behavior in LGU-based Citizen’s Charter initiative. *Journal of Local Governance and Development Studies*, 4(2), 33–48.
- Grindle, M. S. (2017). *Bureaucrats, politicians, and peasants in Mexico: A case study in public policy*. Princeton University Press.
- Hays, J. (2008). Corruption in the Philippines. https://factsanddetails.com/southeast-asia/Philippines/sub5_6f/entry-3906.html
- Jacobini, H. B., & Associates. (1956). *Governmental services in the Philippines*. Institute of Public Administration, University of the Philippines, Manila.
- Joshi, A., & Houtzager, P. P. (2012). Widgets or watchdogs? Conceptual explorations in social accountability. *Public Management Review*, 14(2), 145–162. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2012.657837>
- Kettl, D. F. (2000). The global revolution in public management: Driving themes, missing links. *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*, 19(2), 246–262.
- Lledo, V., & Abinales, P. (2019). Citizen expectations and public service delivery in the Philippines. *Philippine Studies: Historical and Ethnographic Viewpoints*, 67(3–4), 395–416.
- Manasan, R. G. (2016). *An assessment of the performance of the government in delivering basic services* (PIDS Discussion Paper Series No. 2016-24). Philippine Institute for Development Studies. <https://pidswebs.pids.gov.ph/CDN/PUBLICATIONS/pidsdps1624.pdf>
- Mangahas, M. (2020). Socio-economic status and citizen empowerment: A study on public service experiences. *Journal of Philippine Development Studies*, 47(1), 122–143.
- Manila, R. S., & Bunquin, M. B. (2018). Client perceptions on local government services: A study on inclusivity and service delivery. *Philippine Social Sciences Review*, 70(1), 45–68.

- Mendoza, A. T. (2018). The impact of Citizens' Charter in local governance: An empirical study of service delivery reforms in the Philippines. *Philippine Journal of Public Administration*, 62(1), 35–50.
- Mendoza, M. V. (2016). The quality of public services in the Philippines. <https://www.scribd.com/document/346617039/The-Quality-of-Public-Services-in-the-Philippines-Villamejor-Mendoza>
- Mendoza, R. U., & Acheron, J. (2016). Governance challenges and citizen participation in public service delivery: Lessons from the Philippines. *Asian Journal of Political Science*, 24(3), 304–324. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02185377.2016.1237563>
- Mendoza, R. U. (2017). Strengthening public sector service delivery in the Philippines: Challenges and reforms. *Philippine Political Science Journal*, 38(2), 139–159. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01154451.2017.1375714>
- Municipality of Naic. (2020). *Population census of Naic, Cavite*. Philippine Statistics Authority. <https://psa.gov.ph/classification/psgc/barangays/0402115000>
- Oliver, R. L. (1980). A cognitive model of the antecedents and consequences of satisfaction decisions. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 17(4), 460–469.
- Ombudsman. (2018). LGU top government agency with most Ombudsman cases filed in 2017. Office of the Ombudsman. <https://www.ombudsman.gov.ph>
- Osborne, S. P. (2006). The new public governance? *Public Management Review*, 8(3), 377–387. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719030600853022>
- Osborne, S. P., Radnor, Z., & Nasi, G. (2013). A new theory for public service management? Toward a (public) service-dominant approach. *The American Review of Public Administration*, 43(2), 135–158. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0275074012466935>
- Perez, M., & Ilagan, L. (2019). Clients' satisfaction on the frontline services of a government higher educational institution. *European Journal of Education Studies*. <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejes/article/view/2801>
- Raman, W. (2018). Effectiveness of Citizen's Charter in public service delivery: A study on Trishal Municipality and Boilor Union Parishad. <https://journals.indexcopernicus.com/api/file/viewById/423697.pdf>
- Reyes, C. M., & Dela Cruz, A. S. (2021). Assessing the effectiveness of grievance mechanisms in Philippine local government units: A study on Citizen's Charters. *Philippine Journal of Development Communication*, 43(2), 112–131.

- Reyes, D. R., Tigno, J. V., & Cabaero, C. (2019). Public administration in the Philippines: Evolution and challenges. *Asian Review of Public Administration*, 30(1–2), 15–32.
- Romero, M., De Guzman, M., & Cuya-Antonio, O. (2019). Degree of observance of Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act in the Department of Education in Nueva Ecija, Philippines. *Journal of Public Administration and Governance*, 9(3), 142–158. <https://www.macrothink.org/journal/index.php/jpag/article/view/14238>
- Santos, M. A. (2020). Transparency, accountability, and client satisfaction: The role of Citizen’s Charter implementation in Philippine public offices. *Journal of Philippine Governance and Policy*, 14(2), 45–62.
- Santos, R. D. (2020). Grievance redress mechanisms and perceived corruption in Philippine local governments. *Asia Journal of Governance and Public Accountability*, 12(3), 90–105.
- Sison, R. M. (2023). Evaluating the effectiveness of the Citizen’s Charter in selected LGUs in Pangasinan. *Journal of Social Governance and Development*, 12(1), 101–117.
- Soriano, M. S., & Dizon, K. A. (2021). Critical perspectives on service delivery: Educational attainment and client satisfaction with Citizen’s Charter implementation. *Southeast Asian Journal of Governance*, 9(2), 77–92.
- Sta. Maria, V. L., & Lapuz, M. C. (2020). Citizen expectations and service quality: A study of married clients in government transactions. *Southeast Asian Journal of Governance*, 8(2), 88–102.
- Tapales, P. D. (2015). Citizen satisfaction with local government services in the Philippines: Highlights from selected studies. *Philippine Social Sciences Review*, 67(1), 23–42.
- Tapales, P. D., & Villamil, C. T. (2017). Service delivery and citizen satisfaction: A study of selected local government units in the Philippines. *Philippine Social Sciences Review*, 69(2), 21–45.
- Van de Walle, S., & Scott, Z. (2011). The role of public services in state- and nation-building: Exploring lessons from European history for fragile states. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 77(2), 325–346. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020852311399231>
- Villanueva, A. B. (2022). Public service delivery system in state universities and colleges: Controversies and best practices across frontline service. *Journal of Public Sector Management*, 8(1), 44–58.
- Villanueva, M. T., & Dizon, K. A. (2022). Client satisfaction and compliance with RA 9485 in SUCs in Northern Luzon. *Journal of Public Sector Management*, 8(1), 44–58.
- Villanueva, R. M. (2022). Advancing citizen-centered governance: Lessons from Citizen’s Charter implementation in selected Philippine municipalities. *Asian Journal of Public Administration*, 44(1), 89–108. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02598272.2022.2054321>

World Bank. (2018). *World development report 2018: Learning to realize education's promise*. World Bank Group. <https://doi.org/10.1596/978-1-4648-1096-1>